

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

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Integrated Weather, Sea Ice and Ocean Service System (IWICOS)

Demonstration and Validation Report

IWICOS Report No. 5

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Authors (in alphabetic order):

Henrik Steen Andersen, Halla Björg Baldursdóttir, Robin Berglund, Patrick Eriksson, Ríkharður Friðrik Friðriksson, Jyrki Haajanen, Guðmundur Hafsteinsson, Torill Hamre, Katrín Hólm Hauksdóttir, Milla Johansson, Ingibjörg Jonsdottir, Ville Kotovirta, Jouko Launiainen, Jenni Mansner, Morten Lind, Leif T. Pedersen, Roberto Saldo, Stein Sandven, Ari Seinä, Renne Tergujeff and Jouni Vainio

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Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC) Edvard Griegsvei 3A N-5059 Bergen, Norway Phone: + 47 55 29 72 88 Fax: + 47 55 20 00 50 E-mail: Stein.Sandven@nrsc.no	Finnish Institute of Marine Research (FIMR) Lyypekinkuja 3, PO Box 33 FIN-00931 Helsinki, Finland Phone: +358 9 6139 4440 Fax: +358 9 6139 4494 E-Mail: Ari.Seina@fimr.fi	Technical Research Centre of Finland (VTT) Tekniikantie 4B, PO Box 1201, FIN-02044 Espoo, Finland Phone: + 358 9 456 6018 Fax: + 358 9 456 6027 E-Mail: robin.berglund@vtt.fi
Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI) Lyngbyvej 100 DK-2100 Copenhagen, Denmark Phone: + 45 39157350 Fax: + 45 39157390 E-Mail: hsa@dm.dk	Technical University of Denmark (DTU) Danish Center for Remote Sensing, Department of Electromagnetic Systems (EMI), Building 348, Technical University of Denmark, DK-2800 Lyngby, Denmark Phone: + 45 45881444 Fax: + 45 45931634 E-Mail: ltp@emi.dtu.dk	Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO) Bustadvegur 9 IS-150 Reykjavik, Iceland Phone: + 354 522 6000 Fax: + 354 522 6001 E-Mail: thor@vedur.is
Radiomidun ehf (subcontractor to IMO) Grandagar_i 9, P.O. Box 1355, 121 Reykjavik, Iceland Phone: + 354 511 1010 Fax: + 354 511 1020 E-mail: kgisla@eyki.is		

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Executive Summary

Four full-scale demonstrations have been carried out in 2002 (Table 1).

The first of these was carried out for a scientific cruise in the Fram Strait in March. During this period the IWICOS Broker and End-User System (ViewIce client) were demonstrated to crew onboard the Finnish research vessel R/V Aranda, operating around 80°N. Altogether about 1000 files were made available for downloading and 196 files were downloaded to the ship consisting of 66 satellite images, 73 wind forecasts, 25 pressure forecasts and 32 ice drift data files. The Iridium communication satellite was used for data transfer. The IWICOS System operated very satisfactory and the user feedback was positive.

The second onboard demonstration of the IWICOS System was done during Arina Arctica's two cruises to Greenland Waters in May-July and August-September. DMI's thick client, the MIO Viewer, was installed onboard the vessel and used operationally to display and analyse met-ice-ocean observed data and forecasts. Inmarsat-B and -C were used for communication, and a total of 185 data packages consisting of 11 satellite images, 11 ice analyses, 375 pressure forecasts, 375 wind forecasts, 300 wave forecasts, 300 swell forecasts and 13 textual weather forecasts (for Icelandic Waters) were downloaded to the ship. The IWICOS System and the MIO Viewer operated as planned, and the overall user feedback was positive.

The IWICOS project and Icelandic products and clients were demonstrated at a large exhibition in Iceland 4-7 September. The Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition 2002 had more than 18000 visitors, and about 800 exhibitors from 37 countries. During the exhibition, IMO's thin web client and Radiomidun's thick client were demonstrated, and an Icelandic IWICOS brochure distributed. Visitors marked at Captain/Owner were picked out and asked to answer a brief questionnaire. In total 95 captains/owners were interviewed.

The EMI Interactive Java client has been providing sea ice, ocean and meteorological products as a public service throughout 2002. This includes support of specific operations: Lance (March), Ocean Tiger (May) and JRC/BAS (October). Data and information has been generated for both Arctic and Antarctic areas. Users are located world-wide, and web logging mechanisms are being used to generate statistics for use.

Further information on these demonstrations is found in subsequent parts of this report.

Table 1 IWICOS demonstrations in 2002.

Demonstration	Client	Target user groups	Area	Time period
Aranda expedition	ViewIce	Ice navigation support	Fram Strait	March 2002
Arina Arctica voyages to Greenland	MIO Viewer	Navigation	North Atlantic and Greenland Waters	June - September
Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition	Birtir (thin and thick client)	Fisheries	Icelandic Waters	September
Continuous web services	EMI Interactive	many	Arctic and Antarctic	continuous

1 Overall conclusions from the four demonstrations

1.1 ARANDA-demonstration

The Fram Strait field experiment provided a unique challenge for the IWICOS System demonstration in the area, where communication possibilities are limited and expensive to use, and the environment plays a vital role in ship's security and successfully achieving the goals of the experiment.

On 2-22 March 2002 the IWICOS Broker and System was demonstrated in full scale during the Finnish research vessel expedition at the Fram Strait area, around latitude 80°N. Because of poor communication possibilities, the Iridium communication satellite system was used for data transfer, and the number and file sizes of delivered information products and data were put into minimal. This proved to function very well.

Three IWICOS partners participated the demonstration and their roles were: VTT was responsible of the Broker and the Façade (real time portal for IWICOS data), FIMR made available the RADARSAT images and ice drift buoy data, and DMI made available wind and air pressure forecasts.

Altogether about 1000 files were made available via the Façade, and the ship downloaded 196 files consisting of 66 satellite images, 73 wind forecasts, 25 pressure forecasts and 32 ice drift data files. On average 9 files was downloaded in a day, varying between 1-26 files.

The available data was presented to the user via a real time portal - the Façade, which used the IWICOS Broker to fetch the relevant data from the data producers. Because of lack of metadata for some of the products, part of the data was fetched directly from the producers to be presented on the web page of the Façade. The availability of new data was announced to the user as e-mails that were converted to Iridium text messages by a gateway at the satellite system provider. The automatic operation of the facade is controlled by a set of parameters - the profile - which describes the priorities and needs of the user.

In general the IWICOS System operated very satisfactory and the user feedback was very positive. Onboard ship three persons operated the system. The feature, where the user could choose the needed data was considered excellent. Semi-automatic features could be included in downloading procedure. Better information flow between producers, system developers and users should be introduced. Also better user introduction for application handling should be made. Some reliable ways for SAR image correct positioning should be developed. Combination use of ship's radar and SAR images could be considered for better image interpretation and optimal route finding.

1.2 Arina Arctica demonstration

The demonstration aboard the vessel Arina Arctica from Royal Arctic Line was carried out in Greenland and Icelandic waters during two cruises in the period of June – September 2002. The users from Royal Arctic Line represents to a high degree the typical user community in these areas. They rely heavily on daily weather, ocean and ice information for both strategic and tactical navigational purposes. Throughout the demonstration the users were capable of replacing traditional hard copy weather maps with digital meteorological, oceanographic, sea ice data and satellite imagery distributed through an Inmarsat satellite connection. Downloaded products were displayed in the Met-Ice-Ocean Viewer and presented in conjunction with GPS and route related information. The demonstration took place as part of the normal operations aboard the vessel and thus enabled a convenient way to explore the value added from the IWICOS system.

From a system management point of view the IWICOS system functioned well all the way from production to end-user system. Only minor problems in the IWICOS service chain were experienced which meant that 3% of the data packages did not reach the vessel due to server problems at DMI. The interoperability and data exchange between the IWICOS consortium participants was well functioning throughout the demonstration.

From the user side the overall response to the IWICOS system was positive and the basic capabilities for presenting and combining meteorological, oceanographic and sea ice information were widely used throughout the demonstration. Furthermore, some specialised modules were investigated for their

potential concerning route planning. Traditionally users have based their route planning on hard copy weather maps. During this demonstration route planning was aided by using a digital route module within the client software – a module which the users found particularly helpful. The coupling of GPS positional information with route information and weather/ocean data enabled the users to investigate conditions along a given route based on numerical predictions of weather and ocean data. In relation to the future development of the client the implementation of automatic or semi-automatic weather routing should be investigated intensively in close connection with existing weather routing services.

A number of recommendations could be deduced from the response to the questionnaire and from interviews with the ship crew. Thus, further development of the system should address issues like:

- better integration of client with existing navigational equipment, especially in relation to transferring route/waypoint information between the basic navigational system and the client.
- extend products to include frontal zones and positions of high and low pressure zones, i.e. information that is found in traditional analysed weather maps
- easier adjustment of user profile from the client system
- more training of users.

Valuable experience was gained from the Arina Arctica demonstration, especially regarding current system components like the Facade and client. Additionally, experience was gained regarding production, communication, interoperability with end-users and new ideas rose for future initiatives concerning extensions to the client system.

1.3 Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition

The two IWICOS-clients developed in Iceland (IMO's thin client and Radiomidun's thick client) were demonstrated to the target user group, Icelandic fishermen, at The Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition in Kópavogur 4-7 September 2002. 95 "captains/owners" were asked to give their opinion of the clients and the available products after the demonstration.

In general the reaction was very positive. The "single entry access" concept seemed to be popular; people did really like to get access to different products from one site.

There was a general interest in graphical presentation of information but it was also very clear that people did not like to lose the concise presentation of interpreted information they are used to get in traditional textual weather forecasts. Information offered to Icelandic fishermen should therefore contain products of both types which should support each other.

It was also obvious that even within this rather limited user group the needs for products and distribution means are very different. An important factor is the size of the vessel. The bigger vessels are generally well equipped and satellite transmission of data to be processed in a thick client is a feasible choice for them. The smaller vessels, which are not as well equipped, have to rely on mobile phones or Internet connections while staying at home.

Another important factor is the area of operation. Vessels operating off the north and northwest coast of Iceland may often experience arctic conditions, such as ice accretion and encounters with sea ice. In the much warmer waters off the south coast sea ice is hardly ever seen and ice accretion is generally not a big problem. The south coast is on the other hand very exposed to the high waves from the open Atlantic Ocean. The interest for wave forecasts was in fact very prominent among all users but for users operating off the south coast they were definitely the most wanted product.

The answers given may be used as a valuable guideline for development of new products for seafarers in Icelandic waters, both regarding content and methods of presentation.

Weather forecasts in radio and from coastal stations have traditionally been the main source for met-ice-ocean information. Such information is by nature free of charge for the users. Icelandic fishermen are therefore not used to the idea of paying for weather information. Nevertheless considerable understanding was noticed for the fact that it might become necessary to pay for products specially developed, produced and presented to a limited user group. It seemed also acceptable that transmission costs should be paid by the receiver. Some of the "captains/owners" said that they were willing to pay "a reasonable amount" for good information but very few were willing to quantify this amount and suggest a monthly price for subscription.

1.4 Continuous web services

The system was originally developed for internal use at DCRS. The purpose was to enable distance working, and to allow our data collection systems to be supervised from remote places. Project partners and colleagues became very interested in the service, and we decided to open the system up for external use. We now see our main users as universities and other scientific institutions doing arctic research, operational ice centres, shipping companies, fisheries companies, etc. – people with a need for varied and timely information about the marine environment. Our target user group is expected to perform some interpretation of the images themselves, so we see our objectives as providing the tools to make decisions, rather than making the decisions.

All data are automatically gathered from the Internet. We are continuously looking for new data sources, to expand our coverage, to become independent of single sources, and to be able to include new facilities, higher resolution and/or more timely data. The main sources are.

- SSM/I data
- QuikSCAT data
- AMSU data
- NOAA AVHRR data
- Sea Surface Temperature data
- Wind and Wave forecasts
- Digital Ice Charts

Most user feedback has been in connection with the (few) down periods we have had over the past years. A number of items in the view have been introduced as a response to user feedback. Examples are:

- Colour legend
- Date selection
- Image info

Users have also complained about the many subareas, and the long list of images. We are therefore in the process of switching to just two databases/interfaces, one for the northern, and one for the southern hemisphere.

It has been demonstrated that a free Internet service with ice/sea/weather information can be established and it has attracted a large number of users in many fields. The system has proven valuable for internal use as well as for many external users. Running the system, we have gained considerable goodwill amongst science partners and collaborators all over the world.

1.5 Comparison and overall assessment

The Aranda and the Arina Arctica demonstration were both aimed at users at sea with low-level bandwidth connections. Different communication systems were used (Iridium vs. Inmarsat) since the two vessels operated at different latitudes. Both demonstrations used special software for packaging and transmitting data, and no problems caused by the communication systems were noted during the demonstration periods. During the Arina Arctica demonstration, 3% of the data packages could not be delivered, but this was due to server problems onshore. The total amount of data transmitted was approx. 4.6 MBytes for the Aranda demonstration, and approx. 6.6 MBytes for the Arina Arctica demonstration. All together, data transmission was performed satisfactorily in the two demonstrations, and the major “complaint” from users regarding communication was the cost, which the partners tried to keep to a minimum by preparing small-sized products.

The façades and clients used in the two demonstrations were customised to the two different expeditions, and are thus difficult to compare to each other. The general feedback was positive for both demonstrations, with requests for new or enhanced functionality in forthcoming versions of these systems. This suggests the users would like similar services to be available in later cruises, and at the same time showed that the IWICOS architecture facilitated customisation of parts of the delivery chain to accommodate the needs of users working under different (communication) constraints. Both demonstrations furthermore included supply of data from multiple producers, which was also handled by the two production and delivery systems built upon the common system architecture.

The demonstration carried out at the Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition was targeted at captains/owners, of which 95 were interviewed during the exhibition. These interviews documented that the needs for products and processing capabilities differed, and that the vessel size to a large degree determined what type of products and onboard information systems would be most useful. Bigger vessels often had satellite transmission equipment, enabling them to download "larger" products that could be processed in a thick client onboard. Smaller vessels, on the other hand, had to rely on mobile phone or use Internet connection from home before going to sea. Thus, obtaining "smaller" products that were ready for display in a thin client would be a better solution for captains/owners of smaller vessels.

Another important issue brought up at the Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition, was the cost of products and services. Many of the interviewed users initially expressed a reluctance to pay for other than the transmission cost, as they regarded weather information as something that should be available for free. After advocating that such products and services would have to be prepared especially for specific user groups, the interviewed captains/owners were more open to the idea of paid products and services, but it was difficult to get them to quantify how much they could be willing to pay.

The continuous web services operated by DCRS has been the longest running demonstration, as it has been available during most of the 3-year project period. All products provided by this service have been free, escaping the potential problems related to charging users for access. A large number of users have thus been attracted to this service, and the IWICOS project and products promoted to a very wide audience in e.g. science, governmental institutions and industry, as indicated by the excerpt of the web usage statistics given towards the end of this report.

During the IWICOS project, the following user groups have been targeted:

1. Regular users:
 - National ice and weather services (Baltic region, Greenland, Iceland)
 - Shipping companies and sea traffic administration (Baltic, Greenland, Iceland, NSR)
 - Icebreaker captains and ice pilots of ships (Baltic region, Arctic Ocean)
 - Oil companies (Greenland and Arctic Ocean)
 - Fishing vessels (Baltic region, Iceland, Greenland)
 - Coast guard (Iceland)
2. Other users who will need data on more occasional basis:
 - climate research
 - environmental monitoring and assessment
 - navy
 - insurance industry
 - tourism
 - students and teachers
 - media

During the four dedicated demonstrations, representatives from all categories of "regular users" have been exposed to the IWICOS project, products and services, although not for all of the areas listed above. In addition, many representatives from the "other users" category have been reached, both in these demonstrations and through presentations at conferences and workshops. Thus, the IWICOS project has succeeded in demonstrating a suite of met-ice-ocean products to a wide audience, accessing the information through different communication networks ranging from low bandwidth satellite communication to high-speed landbased networks. The demonstrations performed have received overall positive feedback, and many of the involved users have expressed interest in continued and enhanced met-ice-ocean services. The concrete implementations on different computer platforms have shown that the IWICOS system architecture is versatile and can easily be customised to meet the needs of specific user groups. The architecture is built open accepted standards for metadata and data representation, system interfaces and communication protocols, which makes it well suited for future commercialisation of met-ice-ocean services.

Integrated Weather, Sea Ice and Ocean Service System (IWICOS)

IWICOS DEMONSTRATION REPORT:

R/V Aranda demonstration during the Fram Strait expedition in March 2002

Ari Seina, Jouko Launiainen, Patrick Eriksson, Milla Johansson & Jouni Vainio
(FIMR)

Robin Berglund, Jyrki Haajanen, Ville Kotovirta, Jenni Mansner, Renne Tergujeff
(VTT)

Morten Lind (DMI)

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Finnish Institute of Marine Research (FIMR) Lyypekinkuja 3, P.O. Box 33 FIN-00931 Helsinki, Finland Phone: +358 9 6136 4440 Fax: +358 9 6139 4494 E-mail: ari.seina@fimr.fi	Technical Research Centre of Finland (VTT) Tekniikantie 4B, P.O. Box 1201 FIN-002044 Espoo, Finland Phone: +358 9 456 6018 Fax: +358 9 456 6027 E-mail: robin.berglund@vtt.fi
Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI) Lyngbyvej 100 DK-2100 Copenhagen, Denmark Phone: +45 39157350 Fax: +45 39157390 E-mail: mli@dmi.dk	

INVESTIGATORS

FIMR: Ari Seina, Jouko Launiainen, Patrick Eriksson, Milla Johansson & Jouni Vainio

VTT: Robin Berglund, Jyrki Haajanen, Ville Kotovirta, Jenni Mansner, Renne Tergujeff

DMI: Morten Lind

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Executive summary

The Fram Strait experiment (FRAMZY-2002 – Cyclones over the Fram Strait: air-ice-ocean interaction and sea ice transport field experiment, financed mainly by the German Sonderforschungsbereich (SBF 512)) provided a unique challenge for the IWICOS System demonstration at the area, where communication possibilities are limited and expensive to use, and the environment plays a vital role in ship's security and successfully achieving the goals of the experiment.

On 2-22 March 2002 the IWICOS Broker and System was demonstrated during the Finnish research vessel expedition at the Fram Strait area, around latitude 80°N. Because of poor communication possibilities, the Iridium communication satellite system was used for data transfer, and the number and file sizes of delivered information products and data were put into minimal.

Three IWICOS partners participated the demonstration and their roles were: VTT was responsible of the Broker and the Facade (real time portal for IWICOS data), FIMR made available the RADARSAT images and ice drift buoy data, and DMI made available wind and air pressure forecasts.

Altogether about 1000 files were made available for downloading and 196 files were downloaded to the ship consisting of 66 satellite images, 73 wind forecasts, 25 pressure forecasts and 32 ice drift data files.

On average 9 files was downloaded in a day, varying between 1-26 files. Original file sizes were 1.1-81.2 kBytes with an average of 26.5 kBytes. The compressed file sizes were 0.82-25.1 kBytes with an average 13.2 kBytes. All together 4.6 MBytes, (compressed size 2.7 MBytes), were downloaded by the ship. The ship started the file transfer 0:09-19:44 hours, on average 5:00 hours, after metadata was registered with the Broker. During the first ten days most of the files were downloaded, but due to the high communication costs, only 1-6 files a day were downloaded during the rest of the expedition.

The available data was presented to the user via a real time portal - the Facade - which used the IWICOS Broker to fetch the relevant data from the data producers. Because of lack of metadata for some of the products, part of the data was fetched directly from the producers to be presented on the web page of the Facade. The availability of new data was announced to the user as e-mails that were converted to Iridium text messages by a gateway at the satellite system provider. The automatic operation of the facade is controlled by a set of parameters - the profile - which describes the priorities and needs of the user.

In general the IWICOS System operated very satisfactory and the user feedback was positive. Onboard ship three persons operated the system. The feature, where the user could choose the needed data among relevant alternatives, was considered excellent. Semi-automatic features could be included in downloading procedure. Problems were found in some ViewIce application functionalities, like no possibility to use Iridium and ship's intranet simultaneously, and usability of RADARSAT images due to strong ice drift, difficulties in positioning the ship in the image. Also the image interpretation

was occasionally difficult when large areas had the similar grey level, or/and they were covered by frost smoke or frost flowers.

Regarding recommendation for further development the conclusion was that better information flow between producers, system developers and users should be introduced. Also better user introduction or training for application handling should be made. Some reliable ways for SAR image correct positioning should be developed. Combined use of ship's radar and SAR images could be considered for better image interpretation and optimal route finding.

1. Background

The R/V Aranda demonstration was made during the FRAMZY-2002 – Cyclones over the Fram Strait: air-ice-ocean interaction and sea ice transport field experiment, financed mainly by the German Sonderforschungsbereich (SBF 512), and it was taken place at the Fram Strait area in March 2002. Fram Strait lies between Spitsbergen (Svalbard) and Greenland around 80°N (Fig. 1). The main purpose of the field experiment was to study decrease and redistribution of the Arctic sea ice. In the Arctic Ocean, the ice drift is dominated by two large-scale transport regimes: the Transport Drift Stream extending from the Siberian coast to the Fram Strait and the Beaufort Gyre located in the American-Canadian sector of the Arctic. Per annum, an amount of about 10-20% of the Arctic sea ice is transported through the Fram Strait into the Atlantic Ocean. The Arctic freshwater export has an impact on the oceanic density stratification and hence on the conditions for deep convection in the Greenland Sea. This deep convection is considered to be one driving mechanism for the global oceanic circulation.

Figure 1 The Arctic Ocean and the FRAZY-2002 main intensive experiment area of R/V Aranda.

Main objectives of the experiment were:

- Investigate of cyclogenesis (dependence on large-scale baroclinicity, on lee waves generated by the orography of Greenland and Spitsbergen, and on air-flow direction relate to sea ice distribution),
- Investigate the local effect of the cyclones on air-ice interaction, ice drift and ice distribution and, thus on the freshwater flow through the Fram Strait,
- Study the atmosphere-sea ice-ocean interaction in the Arctic Sea areas,

- Study ice transport through the Fram Strait, and
- study atmosphere and ocean forcing.

Participating institutes were the Finnish Institute of Marine Research, Finland and University of Hamburg, Germany.

The main experiment took place on 2-22 March 2002, and three platforms were used:

- Finnish research vessel Aranda anchored at a large ice floe, where she remained stationary during experiment. Onboard ship intensive meteorological and oceanographic observations and studies were made.
- German Falcon research airplane equipped with many high-tech meteorological sensors was based at the Spitsbergen. She made several research flights over the study area.
- 14 ice drift buoys were installed on ice floes and ice drift was studied with these buoys.

2. Role of IWICOS partners

The Fram Strait experiment provided a unique challenge for the IWICOS System demonstration at the area, where communication possibilities are limited and expensive to use, and the environment plays a vital role in ship's security and achieving successfully the goals of the experiment.

Figure 2 Iridium satellite telephone and ViewIce application onboard R/V Aranda during IWICOS demonstration. Over the computer screen a mosaic of RADARSAT images and air pressure field.

Due limited communication possibilities, delivered information products and data were put into minimal. Three IWICOS partners participated in the demonstration and their roles were:

VTT made available ViewIce application onboard ship, tested the communication system functionalities via the Iridium satellite system and hosted the IWICOS Facade and Broker.

FIMR supported the expedition with real time or near real time RADARSAT ScanSAR Wide images and ice drift buoy data.

DMI supported the expedition with meteorological forecasts. Four times a day DMI made available HIRLAM forecasts for 10 m wind and surface air pressure in 3 h steps for next 48 h.

3. Description of the system

Figure 3 shows an overview of the system. In the Aranda demonstration the Broker received metadata from DMI. The Facade then requested metadata from the Broker, received RADARSAT images and buoy data from FIMR, and weather data from DMI.

Figure 3 The IWICOS system in the ARANDA demonstration

The operation of the Facade was controlled by user specific profiles, i.e. parameters that described the needs of the Client (Aranda). The parameters were stored in a

profile database that could be edited via a user interface - the Profile-UI. Based on the profile, the Facade fetched the needed products and formed a password protected web page accessible on the web. A notification was sent to the user when new products were made available. The user could then download selected products from the web page.

The products were visualized with the ViewIce program.

4. R/V Aranda data requirements and IWICOS data to the ship

As the experiment area situated around or north of 80°N this caused communication problems for data transfer to the ship. Available communication satellite systems were Inmarsat with a very slow or expensive data transfer capacity and the fact that the area was out or almost out of satellite's range, and the Iridium satellite system. In practice, the Iridium was the only available and reliable system. However, Iridium was capable to transfer only some 13 kBytes/min. This forced us to limit the data transfer to the minimum set of data needed for the scientific experiment and for the ship's safety. Under the IWICOS demonstration only satellite, weather and buoy data were delivered to R/V Aranda. The data was made available to the ship via the IWICOS Facade and Broker and consisted of the RADARSAT images, weather forecasts and ice drift buoy data.

Figure 4 ViewIce application onboard ship showing combination of ship's position (yellow circle), position of ice drift buoys (triangles), and wind field (red and blue) seen over the RADARSAT image in 12 March 2002.

Altogether about 1000 files were made available for downloading and 196 files were downloaded to the ship consisting of 66 satellite images, 73 wind forecasts, 25 pressure forecasts and 32 ice drift data files.

The metadata information was put into the IWICOS Broker several times a day. At the R/V Aranda the data downloading started on average after 5h 00' after the

message was stored in the Broker: Minimum time for starting data transfer was 0h 09', and maximum was 19h 44'.

4.1 Satellite data

RADARSAT ScanSAR Wide images were delivered on daily basis to R/V Aranda. ScanSAR Wide screen covers about 500*500 km area and its spatial resolution is about 100 m. A contract with the Tromsø Satellite Station was made, where the TSS made available 25 scenes of which 20 scenes could be downloaded. At the ice service processing and downloading took less than two hours, including data transfer to the ship no more than three hours. Downloading, reprocessing, geographical correction, land masking and format change were done before scenes were available for transferring. This was done at the FIMR's Finnish Ice Service. (Figure 2 and Figure 4).

Because of large file sizes, two types of images were produced: a full-cover overview image in about 1 km resolution, and sub-images covering about ~ 100*100 km, where the full-resolution images were cut into 29 sub-images in a 100-200 m resolution. This put largest file sizes down smaller than 100 kBytes.

Table 1. Downloaded RADARSAT images to the R/V Aranda.

Date	Large images	Sub-images	Total
02.03.2002	1	1	2
03.03.2002	0	0	0
04.03.2002	1	5	6
05.03.2002	1	4	5
06.03.2002	1	9	10
07.03.2002	1	10	11
08.03.2002	1	2	3
09.03.2002	1	2	3
10.03.2002	1	2	3
11.03.2002	1	3	4
12.03.2002	1	2	3
13.03.2002	1	4	5
14.03.2002	0	1	1
15.03.2002	0	2	2
16.03.2002	0	2	2
17.03.2002	0	0	0
18.03.2002	1	1	2
19.03.2002	0	1	1
20.03.2002	0	1	1
21.03.2002	1	1	2
22.03.2002	0	0	0
Sum	13	53	66
Avg./day	0,7	2,8	3,5

Totally 19 large images and 551 sub-images were made available on the IWICOS Facade. Totally 66 images were downloaded to R/V Aranda: 13 large-cover, low resolution images and 53 sub-images (Table 1 and 2, Figure 5 and Figure 6). On average between 2 and 22 March 3.5 images were downloaded daily, varying from 0 to 11 images. Minimum original file size was 6.261 kBytes, average size 18.565 kBytes and maximum size was 25.882 kBytes. Taking into account the maximum lossless compression of 3%, the compressed sizes were minimum 6.073 kBytes, average 18.008 kBytes and maximum 25.106 kBytes respectively. Data transfer started 1:55-9:09 hours, on average 4:29 after message was put into the Broker.

Figure 5 Number of RADARSAT images transferred to R/V Aranda 2-21 March 2002.

4.2 Meteorological data

Meteorological data consisted of mean sea level pressure and 10 m wind. The Danish Meteorological Institute made this data available via the IWICOS Broker four times a day.

The data consisted of:

Mean sea level pressure:

- Analysis: 00, 06, 12, 18 Z
- Prognosis: +3, +6, +9...+45, +48 h
- Extent: 83N 15W - 83N 15E; 73N 15W - 73N 15E
- Resolution: 2 deg. long. ; 0.3 deg. lat.
- Grid size: 300
- Estimated file size: 11 kBytes

10 m wind:

- Analysis: 00, 06, 12, 18 Z
- Prognosis: +3, +6, +9...+45, +48 h
- Extent:
 - Area 1: 83N 10W - 83N 00E; 80N 10W - 80N 00E
 - Area 2: 83N 00W - 83N 10E; 80N 00W - 80N 10E
 - Area 3: 83N 10W - 83N 00E; 77N 10W - 77N 00E
 - Area 4: 80N 00W - 80N 10E; 77N 00W - 77N 10E
 - Area 5: 81.5N 05W - 81.5N 05E; 78.5N 05W - 78.5N 05E
- Resolution: 1 deg. long. ; 0.15 deg. lat.
- Grid size: 200
- Estimated file size: 14.5 kBytes

Table 2. Number of downloaded data files to the R/V Aranda 2-22 March 2002 under IWICOS demonstration.

Date	RADARSAT images	10m wind forecasts	Air pressure forecasts	Buoy data	Sum
02.03.2002	2	4	1	1	8
03.03.2002	0	4	1	2	7
04.03.2002	6	10	2	2	20
05.03.2002	5	10	2	2	19
06.03.2002	10	5	1	2	18
07.03.2002	11	10	2	3	26
08.03.2002	3	5	2	3	13
09.03.2002	3	2	1	1	7
10.03.2002	3	6	2	2	13
11.03.2002	4	1	1	2	8
12.03.2002	3	1	1	1	6
13.03.2002	5	4	1	2	12
14.03.2002	1	1	1	1	4
15.03.2002	2	2	1	1	6
16.03.2002	2	1	1	0	4
17.03.2002	0	2	1	2	5
18.03.2002	2	1	1	1	5
19.03.2002	1	2	1	1	5
20.03.2002	1	1	1	1	4
21.03.2002	2	1	1	1	5
22.03.2002	0	0	0	1	1
Sum	66	73	25	32	196
Avg/day.	3,1	3,5	1,2	1,5	9,3

About 80 10 m wind forecasts and 400 air pressure forecast fields were made available for transfer via the IWICOS Broker (Figure 6). Totally 98 meteorological forecasts were downloaded to the R/V Aranda: 73 wind forecasts and 25 air pressure forecasts (Table 2, Figure 6.). On average 3.5 wind forecasts and 1.2 pressure forecasts were downloaded daily, varying from 0 to 10 files. Minimum file size for wind forecasts was 1.094 kBytes, (with 25% compression 0.821 Kbytes) average was

16.195 Kbytes (12.146 Kbytes) and maximum 17.504 Kbytes (13.128 kBytes). For minimum pressure forecasts this was 1.105 kBytes (with 8% compression 1.017 kBytes), average size 16.884 kBytes (15.533 kBytes) and maximum of 17.680 kBytes (16.266 kBytes). Data transfer for wind forecasts started 3:20-19:44 hours, on average 6:45 hours and for air pressure forecasts 3:23-10:29 hours, on average 6:12 hours after the message was put into the Broker. Late downloading of wind and pressure forecasts was mainly because the 00Z forecasts were downloaded earliest in the morning or later, when this data was needed for verification of local observations. Latest 00Z downloading of wind forecast took place in the next evening at 19:44Z.

Figure 6 Number of files downloaded to the R/V Aranda via the IWICOS Broker 2-22 March 2002.

4.3 Buoy data

Totally 14 Argos ice drift buoys were mounted at the area. Data of these buoys were collected via Argos at the FIMR, files transferred into XML format and made available to download via the IWICOS Facade to the ship (Fig. 6 and 13).

Buoy position files were made available once an hour for transfer via the IWICOS Facade. This was too large a number to transfer via the slow communication system to the ship. Thus only 32 buoy data files were downloaded (Table 2, Figure 6.). On average 1.5 files were transferred a day, varying from 0 to 3 files. Minimum file size was 30.510 kBytes (with 87% compression 3.966 kBytes), average size 54.420 kBytes (7.075 kBytes) and maximum size was 81.198 kBytes (10.556 kBytes). Data transfer started 0:09-2:20 hours, on average 0:37 after message was put into the Broker.

Figure 7 R/V Aranda and one of Argos ice drift buoys.

5. Detailed description of the system

In this chapter a detailed description of the system is given.

5.1 Producer servers

A producer server consisted of two parts, active and passive [HaB01]. The active part informed Broker when a new product was available or an old product was outdated. The passive part was a web server where the active part placed its output for the Broker and the Facades to be retrieved. The main components of the Producer Server is shown in Figure 8

Figure 8 The IWICOS Producer Server components

In the Aranda demonstration the necessary data was provided by two producers, DMI and FIMR. The DMI producer server functioned as a normal producer server. It sent metadata to the Broker and offered weather data in GRIB format for the Facade to be retrieved.

Due to a tight schedule, FIMR was unable to generate broker compatible metadata of RADARSAT images or buoy data. To solve this problem, FIMR created a folder on a web server where data was placed. The Facade checked periodically if new data was available. When new data was available, the Facade created internally a metadata-object and handled it as normal metadata from Broker.

5.2 Broker

As described in the previous section, the producer server informed the Broker of new and outdated products [HaB01]. This was done using SOAP messages (Figure 9). The Producer server stored the available products on a web server. The Broker parsed the contents of the metadata and extracts all elements applicable to the MSS (Minimal Searchable Set) format to its database. The Broker had the information of available products from different producers and the information of where the products could be found.

The Facade queried the Broker about available products [HaB01]. The queries were based on XML-format and were sent as SOAP messages. The query could be posed in two modes: brief and full. In the former, the response contained only the MSS. In the latter the response contained the actual product metadata.

Figure 9 The IWICOS Producer Server and Broker.

5.3 Facade

The Facade consisted of two main modules: Metadata & Product Manager and Profile Manager [Kot02]. The Profile manager provided the user with a User Interface to manage profile data, i.e. parameters that described the needs of the user. The profile data was stored in a database. Metadata and Product Manager retrieved the profile data from the database and fetched the products needed from the Producer servers based on the profile. The Facade stored the retrieved products on a web page and send a notification to the user (if a notification was specified in the profile parameters).

Figure 10. The IWICOS Facade's main modules.

5.3.1 Metadata and product manager

The Metadata and product manager was controlled by the profile [Kot02]. It checked periodically if new data, which was interesting according to the profile, was available. When new product data was available, the Facade retrieved the data, stored it in a local file and generated a web page with links to the products. The generated web page is shown in Figure 11. The idea was to present only relevant information to the user and when many alternatives existed, the alternatives were arranged in order of anticipated importance. A criteria for relevance could be the distance of the centre of the image with respect to the current position of the ship.

The Facade sent a notification of new products available to the user according to the profile. The notification was implemented as an e-mail, which could be relayed as text messages to Iridium using an Iridium gateway or as SMS messages to a GSM phone using an SMS gateway. A parameter, called the Quarantine time, was used to prevent the user from being flooded by messages. This parameter prohibited sending of a notification if the previous message already was sent within the quarantine time interval.

5.3.2 Profile manager

The Profile manager consisted of two parts: FacadeDB and Profile-UI [Kot02]. The FacadeDB was a profile parameter database. Profile-UI was the user interface to manage the profile data which is described more in detail in paragraph 5.4.

Figure 11 The IWICOS Product list Page (the IWICOS Facade)

5.4 Profile-UI

Profile-UI was the User Interface to manage profile data. The Profile-UI provided a web browser interface to edit the profile parameters. There were two versions of the user interface: a simple and a full version. The simple version was intended for the end user (Aranda) where the communication was limited. The simple version enabled the users to change the information about their current position only. The full version enabled editing of other parameters in the profile as well. Figure 12 shows the full version of the Profile-UI.

Figure 12. The IWICOS Profile-UI full version

5.5 Communication System

Data transfer was performed using the IRIDIUM satellite communication system. On the client computer emulator software (called Apollo Emulator) was installed. This software took care of opening the session via the IRIDIUM gateway to the desired Internet address.

Figure 13 IRIDIUM Direct Internet connection

The Apollo emulator software emulated a normal LAN connection to the applications, thus standard web browsing and e-mail software could be used. The data to be downloaded were selected and downloaded using MS Internet Explorer. The emulator software also included data compression functionality, which reduced the time to transfer ASCII files like the buoy data.

The IRIDIUM phone was a Motorola 9500 with a data-adaptor and external antenna. (Figure 2). An RS-232 serial cable connected the phone to the computer.

5.6 ViewIce

In the Aranda demonstration ViewIce (Figure 14) was used to display wind and pressure forecasts, RADARSAT images and buoy data. The user downloaded the images from the web page that the Facade generated according to the user's profile. The selected data was saved in a local file from where ViewIce could display it.

Figure 13 Combination of RADARSAT image, buoy positions (triangles), surface air pressure field (black) and 10 m wind field (blue) onboard ship seen over the ViewIce application.

6. User comments

Onboard the ship three persons operated the System. One of them had had special introduction for the System use beforehand by the VTT. Two users filled out the straw polls and were interviewed for functionalities of the System and products.

In general the IWICOS System operated very satisfactory. The feature, where the user could choose the needed data was considered excellent. Semi-automatic features could be included in downloading procedure. Problems were found in:

- some ViewIce application functionalities,
- not possible to use Iridium and ship's intranet simultaneously, and
- usability of RADARSAT images due strong ice drift, difficulties in positioning the ship in the image, and the image interpretation was sometimes difficult, when large areas had the similar colour and / frost smoke and conditions were frost flowers were over the ice, hampered interpretation of ice conditions.

Straw poll answers from two main users showed:

TECHNICAL FUNCTIONALITY:

Have the ViewIce application functioned well? If not, what kind of problems have there been?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Occasionally the application slowed down significantly. In the beginning the image display on the screen was fast, towards end of experiment this took a long time. • Difficulties to draw the buoy tracks correctly. All buoys were not visible all the time though the data was included in the files. <p><i>Comment:</i> Application was running a long time without turning off. Thus the memory filled up because a still unknown reason. The buoy data might have contained some gaps in the time series, but this still needs some investigation.</p>

Have the data downloading functioned well? What kind of problems have you concountered?
Difficulties to connect in to the Iridium satellite
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No problems
Difficulties to connect in data downloading
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No problems. Iridium application kept for some time the connection open when data was not downloaded.
Difficulties to connect in to the web server
No problems. Iridium Apollo emulator kept the connection open for some time when data was not downloaded. Comment: This could be easy to arrange.
Difficulties to download the data to the PC
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No problems.
Forced to start the data downloading many times?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None.
Have needed information been easy to find?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None.

SYSTEM USE:

How often has the system been used? Who have the users been?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once or twice a day. There were three users.
How may RADARSAT images have you downloaded?
<ul style="list-style-type: none">
Which areas have been covered the RADARSAT images?
<ul style="list-style-type: none">
Have you downloaded weather forecasts and how often?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once a day.
Have you used buoy data?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Because there were problems using ViewIce in drawing buoy positions with a negative longitude, XML-files were drawn using other applications, like Matlab. From the files meteorological buoy measurements have been observed. <p><i>Comment:</i> There was a trivial error in the ViewIce buoy drawing programme.</p>

BENEFITS:

Do you have examples of benefits using image data? When image data have effect to your decisions? Which especial images have been useful (image names:)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Large-scale ice concentration information has been used in making the decisions. There have been difficulties in finding out the correct ship's position due fast ice drift in the area. This complicated the image usability in e.g. lead finding.
Opinions about image interpretation? Have there been difficulties and should there also be an ice chart available?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Image interpretation was sometimes difficult, when large areas had the similar colour. Frost smoke and conditions were frost flowers were over the ice, hampered interpretation of ice conditions. An ice chart would not help in image interpretation. <p><i>Comment:</i> There were three possible error sources: inaccurate coast-line, incorrect land mask and/or RADARSAT position was incorrect. Radar echo of the ship could help. Two kind of satellite images could be produced, a very high-resolution image around the small area around the ship and lower resolution covering larger area. Using the high-resolution image ship's radar echo could be identified out and correct position of the larger image could be made more accurate.</p>
Have the image data been fresh enough?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes. Fresher could not be possible. <p><i>Comment:</i> Due to fast ice drift ice conditions were radically changed in a few hours.</p>
Have there been benefits combining image and weather data? Examples?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes. Weather data and forecast with Time Slider were a good way of presenting information. <p><i>Comment:</i> Users were trying to use all possible data and forecasts and combine these and use these for experiment planning.</p>
Have the needs of ARANDA been taken care of enough?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The PC with ViewIce was not placed at the bridge, thus exploitation of it was difficult in navigation.

Comment: Combination of ship's radar and SAR image could bring in extra information in the areas where ice drift is not so fast as in the Fram Strait area.

IDEAS FOR FURTHER DEVELOPMENT:

For data downloading
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In general very good. Excellent feature was that the user could choose the needed data. <p>Comment: In order to help the expedition, in the web side nine closest SAR sub-images, weather forecast areas and latest Argos buoy data files were shown. These were selected from all the data using the latest ship's position information. The ship's position information was not always up-to-date, although the IWICOS Profile-UI full version was in use. Information about updating the Profile-UI newer reached the users onboard the ship. A helpful attribute to ViewIce could be possibility to generate a map showing satellite image candidates for downloading. A help map could be downloaded once and files every time connected to the Broker.</p>
For information presentation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The clarity of positioning was difficult. ViewIce did not include display of coordinate grids. We made a separate file over the Fram Strait (Route file format) for this purpose. Image positioning was difficult. The PC was placed too far from the bridge and thus the information was forced to be printed before it was in use at the bridge.
For collecting the information
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each individual file was downloaded separately. It could be easier for user to mark the need files before downloading.
Other ideas for development and comments
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility to print the screen directly. Simultaneous use of Iridium and ship's intranet.
Are there any special things or functionalities the system is missing?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lat-Long grid

7. Lessons for IWICOS System development

General

Some trivial annoyances could be avoided if there would be a better information flow between the producers, system developers and users. One of them was met when the application was running a long time without turning off. Thus the computer memory became full. Also when changes for the System use was made the information did not necessary reach the users.

IWICOS System:

The System should be flexible in order to avoid things, where new possibilities could not be used onboard ship before reinstallation of presentation application. Thus downloading and presentation applications should be separate.

Presentation application

Better user introducing for application handling should be made. This is more important when users are not scientists well acquainted in using computers, but sea captains and mates. Also when easier procedures are developed, users should introduce themselves to these independently. A helpful addition to ViewIce could be a possibility to generate a map showing satellite image candidates for downloading. A help map would need to be downloaded only once and only files every time when connected to the Broker.

Data and forecasts

Satellite images, weather forecasts and ice drift buoy data delivered during the expedition were considered very good to excellent. For users in other areas where ice drift is not playing such a major role in satellite image interpretation, image positioning should be more accurate. During the expedition there were three possible error sources: inaccurate coast-line, incorrect land mask and/or the RADARSAT position information in the original image was incorrect. Radar echo of the ship could help. Two kinds of satellite images could be produced: a very high-resolution image around the small area around the ship and less high resolution covering larger area. Using the high-resolution image ship's radar echo could be identified out and correct position of the larger image could be made more accurate. Combination of videotaped ship's radar signature and SAR image could bring in extra information in the areas where ice drift is not so fast as in the Fram Strait area. This could help for e.g. in navigable lead identification.

Communication

Iridium communication satellite system used provided to fulfil the needs, although data transfer capacity and speed were modest.

8. Conclusions

The Fram Strait field experiment provided a unique challenge for the IWICOS System demonstration in the area, where communication possibilities are limited and expensive to use, and the environment plays a vital role in ship's security and successfully achieving the goals of the experiment.

On 2-22 March 2002 the IWICOS Broker and System was demonstrated during the Finnish research vessel expedition at the Fram Strait area, around latitude 80°N. Because of poor communication possibilities, the Iridium communication satellite system was used for data transfer, and the number and file sizes of delivered information products and data were put into minimal. This proved to function very well.

Three IWICOS partners participated the demonstration and their roles were: VTT was responsible of the Broker and the Facade (real time portal for IWICOS data), FIMR made available the RADARSAT images and ice drift buoy data, and DMI made available wind and air pressure forecasts.

Altogether about 1000 files were made available for downloading and 196 files (~20%) were downloaded to the ship consisting of 66 satellite images, 73 wind

forecasts, 25 pressure forecasts and 32 ice drift data files. On average 9 files was downloaded in a day, varying between 1-26 files.

The available data was presented to the user via a real time portal - the Facade - which used the IWICOS Broker to fetch the relevant data from the data producers. Because of lack of metadata for some of the products, part of the data was fetched directly from the producers to be presented on the web page of the Facade. The availability of new data was announced to the user as e-mails that were converted to Iridium text messages by a gateway at the satellite system provider. The automatic operation of the facade is controlled by a set of parameters - the profile - which describes the priorities and needs of the user.

In general the IWICOS System operated very satisfactory and the user feedback was very positive. Onboard ship three persons operated the system. The feature, where the user could choose the needed data was considered excellent. Semi-automatic features could be included in downloading procedure. Better information flow between producers, system developers and users should be introduced. Also better user introduction for application handling should be made. Some reliable ways for SAR image correct positioning should be developed. Combination use of ship's radar and SAR images could be considered for better image interpretation and optimal route finding.

References

- [HaB01] Jyrki Haajanen, Robin Berglund, "A SOAP Based Metadata Service – IWICOS Broker", 2001. EOGEO 2001, June 26th - 28th, Fredericton, New Brunswick, Canada (www.digitalearth.ca/pdf/DE_A_222.PDF)
- [Kot02] Ville Kotovirta, "VTT Facade's Metadata & Product Manager Documentation 0.2", IWICOS technical document 2002.

Appendix 1. List of data downloaded to R/V Aranda 2-22 March 2002

RADARSAT images			Wind		
Date and time UTC	File name	File size	Date and time UTC	File name	File size
2.3.2002 8:20:19	FR_A0_020225161607.wvl	13243	25.2.2002 17:21	Wind-area2-20020225060000-DMI.grb	17504
2.3.2002 8:30:16	FR_D3_020225161607.wvl	9828	2.3.2002 8:20	Wind-area3-20020302000000-DMI.grb	17504
4.3.2002 20:46:54	FR_C4_020304161203.wvl	17677	2.3.2002 8:21	Wind-area5-20020302000000-DMI.grb	17504
4.3.2002 20:47:10	FR_C4_020304161203.wvl	17677	2.3.2002 8:26	Wind-area2-20020302000000-DMI.grb	17504
4.3.2002 20:49:07	FR_D4_020304161203.wvl	19858	2.3.2002 8:28	Wind-area1-20020302000000-DMI.grb	17504
4.3.2002 20:50:28	FR_C3_020304161203.wvl	18302	3.3.2002 9:41	Wind-area5-20020303060000-DMI.grb	17504
4.3.2002 20:51:49	FR_D3_020304161203.wvl	17953	3.3.2002 9:42	Wind-area3-20020303060000-DMI.grb	17504
4.3.2002 20:53:05	FR_C5_020304161203.wvl	17514	3.3.2002 9:43	Wind-area4-20020303060000-DMI.grb	17504
5.3.2002 21:26:41	FR_C2_020304161203.wvl	25509	3.3.2002 9:44	Wind-area2-20020303060000-DMI.grb	17504
5.3.2002 21:28:21	FR_D2_020304161203.wvl	16733	4.3.2002 8:16	Wind-area5-20020304000000-DMI.grb	17504
5.3.2002 21:29:32	FR_D5_020304161203.wvl	17901	4.3.2002 8:18	Wind-area3-20020304000000-DMI.grb	17504
5.3.2002 21:31:21	FR_B3_020304161203.wvl	16388	4.3.2002 8:19	Wind-area4-20020304000000-DMI.grb	17504
5.3.2002 21:33:42	FR_A0_020304161203.wvl	22575	4.3.2002 8:20	Wind-area1-20020304000000-DMI.grb	17504
6.3.2002 9:53:53	FR_A0_020306065444.wvl	20729	4.3.2002 8:22	Wind-area2-20020304000000-DMI.grb	17504
6.3.2002 11:05:32	FR_C3_020306065444.wvl	16598	4.3.2002 20:44	Wind-area5-20020304120000-DMI.grb	1094
6.3.2002 11:07:28	FR_D3_020306065444.wvl	18059	4.3.2002 20:44	Wind-area4-20020304120000-DMI.grb	1094
6.3.2002 11:08:43	FR_C4_020306065444.wvl	18644	4.3.2002 20:45	Wind-area3-20020304120000-DMI.grb	1094
6.3.2002 11:09:58	FR_D4_020306065444.wvl	16171	4.3.2002 20:45	Wind-area2-20020304120000-DMI.grb	1094
6.3.2002 11:11:02	FR_C2_020306065444.wvl	6261	4.3.2002 20:46	Wind-area1-20020304120000-DMI.grb	1094
6.3.2002 11:11:35	FR_D2_020306065444.wvl	10441	5.3.2002 10:12	Wind-area5-20020305060000-DMI.grb	17504
6.3.2002 11:12:20	FR_C5_020306065444.wvl	18496	5.3.2002 10:14	Wind-area4-20020305060000-DMI.grb	17504
6.3.2002 11:13:36	FR_D5_020306065444.wvl	16030	5.3.2002 10:15	Wind-area3-20020305060000-DMI.grb	17504
6.3.2002 11:16:18	FR_B3_020306065444.wvl	11643	5.3.2002 10:16	Wind-area2-20020305060000-DMI.grb	17504
7.3.2002 18:41:29	FR_A0_020307162434.wvl	23032	5.3.2002 10:17	Wind-area1-20020305060000-DMI.grb	17504
7.3.2002 18:43:21	FR_C2_020307162434.wvl	25882	5.3.2002 21:20	Wind-area5-20020305180000-DMI.grb	17504
7.3.2002 18:46:11	FR_D2_020307162434.wvl	24293	5.3.2002 21:21	Wind-area3-20020305180000-DMI.grb	2676
7.3.2002 18:48:44	FR_B4_020307162434.wvl	18182	5.3.2002 21:22	Wind-area4-20020305180000-DMI.grb	17504
7.3.2002 18:49:58	FR_D5_020307162434.wvl	15945	5.3.2002 21:23	Wind-area1-20020305180000-DMI.grb	17504
7.3.2002 18:51:13	FR_C3_020307162434.wvl	17943	5.3.2002 21:24	Wind-area2-20020305180000-DMI.grb	17504
7.3.2002 18:52:27	FR_D3_020307162434.wvl	17213	6.3.2002 9:57	Wind-area5-20020306060000-DMI.grb	17504
7.3.2002 18:53:45	FR_C4_020307162434.wvl	17546	6.3.2002 9:58	Wind-area3-20020306060000-DMI.grb	17504
7.3.2002 18:55:30	FR_D4_020307162434.wvl	16750	6.3.2002 9:59	Wind-area4-20020306060000-DMI.grb	17504
7.3.2002 18:56:41	FR_C5_020307162434.wvl	16102	6.3.2002 10:01	Wind-area1-20020306060000-DMI.grb	17504
7.3.2002 21:14:53	FR_C4_020307162434.wvl	17546	6.3.2002 10:02	Wind-area2-20020306060000-DMI.grb	17504
8.3.2002 16:43:57	FR_C4_020308073635.wvl	17732	7.3.2002 8:17	Wind-area5-20020307000000-DMI.grb	17504
8.3.2002 16:45:07	FR_C3_020308073635.wvl	17987	7.3.2002 8:18	Wind-area3-20020307000000-DMI.grb	17504
8.3.2002 16:46:17	FR_A0_020308073635.wvl	20354	7.3.2002 8:19	Wind-area4-20020307000000-DMI.grb	17504
9.3.2002 10:31:15	FR_A0_020309070717.wvl	21736	7.3.2002 8:21	Wind-area1-20020307000000-DMI.grb	17504
9.3.2002 10:32:40	FR_C4_020309070717.wvl	20457	7.3.2002 8:22	Wind-area2-20020307000000-DMI.grb	17504
9.3.2002 10:34:06	FR_C3_020309070717.wvl	20170	7.3.2002 16:22	Wind-area4-20020307060000-DMI.grb	17504
10.3.2002 18:32:33	FR_A0_020310163706.wvl	23143	7.3.2002 16:23	Wind-area5-20020307060000-DMI.grb	17504
10.3.2002 18:34:16	FR_C4_020310163706.wvl	17285	7.3.2002 16:24	Wind-area3-20020307060000-DMI.grb	17504
10.3.2002 18:35:23	FR_C3_020310163706.wvl	17932	7.3.2002 16:26	Wind-area2-20020307060000-DMI.grb	17504

RADARSAT images			Wind		
Date and time UTC	File name	File size	Date and time UTC	File name	File size
11.3.2002 12:38:49	FR_C4_020311074904.wvl	20330	7.3.2002 16:27	Wind-area1-20020307060000-DMI.grb	17504
11.3.2002 12:40:03	FR_C3_020311074904.wvl	20255	8.3.2002 8:20	Wind-area5-20020308000000-DMI.grb	17504
11.3.2002 12:42:07	FR_A0_020311074904.wvl	23339	8.3.2002 8:21	Wind-area2-20020308000000-DMI.grb	17504
11.3.2002 12:43:48	FR_C5_020311074904.wvl	20529	8.3.2002 8:22	Wind-area1-20020308000000-DMI.grb	17504
12.3.2002 16:09:10	FR_A0_020312071949.wvl	23757	8.3.2002 8:24	Wind-area4-20020308000000-DMI.grb	17504
12.3.2002 16:10:47	FR_C4_020312071949.wvl	20470	8.3.2002 8:25	Wind-area3-20020308000000-DMI.grb	17504
12.3.2002 16:12:58	FR_C3_020312071949.wvl	20761	9.3.2002 9:42	Wind-area3-20020309060000-DMI.grb	17504
13.3.2002 21:17:18	FR_C4_020313164937.wvl	17482	9.3.2002 10:35	Wind-area5-20020309060000-DMI.grb	17504
13.3.2002 21:18:24	FR_C3_020313164937.wvl	18267	10.3.2002 8:20	Wind-area5-20020310000000-DMI.grb	17504
13.3.2002 21:20:32	FR_A0_020313164937.wvl	23543	10.3.2002 8:21	Wind-area4-20020310000000-DMI.grb	17504
13.3.2002 21:37:08	FR_D3_020313164937.wvl	17995	10.3.2002 8:22	Wind-area1-20020310000000-DMI.grb	17504
13.3.2002 21:38:16	FR_D4_020313164937.wvl	14731	10.3.2002 8:23	Wind-area1-20020310000000-DMI.grb	17504
14.3.2002 21:23:51	FR_C4_020314162022.wvl	19079	10.3.2002 8:24	Wind-area2-20020310000000-DMI.grb	17504
15.3.2002 12:06:47	FR_D4_020315073219.wvl	21031	10.3.2002 8:38	Wind-area5-20020310120000-DMI.grb	17504
15.3.2002 12:08:05	FR_C4_020315073219.wvl	20415	11.3.2002 12:36	Wind-area5-20020311060000-DMI.grb	17504
16.3.2002 19:16:10	FR_D4_020316170209.wvl	14767	12.3.2002 9:39	Wind-area5-20020312060000-DMI.grb	17504
16.3.2002 19:17:06	FR_C4_020316170209.wvl	16572	13.3.2002 8:31	Wind-area5-20020313000000-DMI.grb	17504
18.3.2002 13:24:35	FR_A0_020318074452.wvl	23891	13.3.2002 8:32	Wind-area4-20020313000000-DMI.grb	17504
18.3.2002 16:26:09	FR_D4_020318074452.wvl	20806	13.3.2002 8:33	Wind-area2-20020313000000-DMI.grb	17504
19.3.2002 10:11:03	FR_D4_020319071537.wvl	19869	13.3.2002 21:19	Wind-area5-20020313120000-DMI.grb	17504
20.3.2002 21:30:22	FR_D4_020320164527.wvl	17272	14.3.2002 11:17	Wind-area5-20020314060000-DMI.grb	17504
21.3.2002 11:00:42	FR_D4_020321075725.wvl	17708	15.3.2002 12:09	Wind-area5-20020315060000-DMI.grb	17504
21.3.2002 14:10:38	FR_A0_020321075725.wvl	20949	15.3.2002 12:15	Wind-area5-20020315060000-DMI.grb	17504
			16.3.2002 9:22	Wind-area5-20020316060000-DMI.grb	17504
			17.3.2002 8:20	Wind-area5-20020317000000-DMI.grb	17504
			17.3.2002 10:18	Wind-area5-20020317060000-DMI.grb	17504
			18.3.2002 11:17	Wind-area5-20020318060000-DMI.grb	17504
			19.3.2002 8:38	Wind-area5-20020319000000-DMI.grb	17504
			19.3.2002 10:08	Wind-area5-20020319060000-DMI.grb	17504
			20.3.2002 19:44	Wind-area5-20020320060000-DMI.grb	17504
			21.3.2002 10:58	Wind-area5-20020321060000-DMI.grb	17504

Compression (bytes)

Compression (bytes)

	Without	With		Without	With
Number of files	66		Number of files	74	
Minimum file size	6261	6073	Minimum file size	1094	821
Average file size	18565	18008	Average file size	16195	12146
Maximum file size	25882	25106	Maximum file size	17504	13128

Downloading starting time after data was ready

	Minimum	Average	Maximum
RADARSAT images	1:15	4:29	9:09
Wind forecasts	3:20	6:45	19:44
Pressure forecasts	3:23	6:12	10:28
Buoy data	0:09	0:37	2:20
Min, avg, max	0:09	5:00	19:44

Pressure			Buoy		
Date and time UTC	File name	File size	Date and time UTC	File name	File size
2.3.2002 8:24	Pressure-20020302000000-DMI.grb	17680	2.3.2002 8:18	Buoys-20020302080100-FIMR.xml	47034
3.3.2002 9:46	Pressure-20020303060000-DMI.grb	17680	3.3.2002 9:47	Buoys-20020303090100-FIMR.xml	48968
4.3.2002 8:23	Pressure-20020304000000-DMI.grb	17680	3.3.2002 17:24	Buoys-20020303170100-FIMR.xml	61447
4.3.2002 20:46	Pressure-20020304120000-DMI.grb	1105	4.3.2002 8:28	Buoys-20020304080100-FIMR.xml	51045
5.3.2002 10:19	Pressure-20020305060000-DMI.grb	17680	4.3.2002 20:54	Buoys-20020304200100-FIMR.xml	72106
5.3.2002 21:25	Pressure-20020305180000-DMI.grb	17680	5.3.2002 10:21	Buoys-20020305080100-FIMR.xml	57131
6.3.2002 9:56	Pressure-20020306060000-DMI.grb	17680	5.3.2002 21:32	Buoys-20020305210100-FIMR.xml	81198
7.3.2002 8:24	Pressure-20020307000000-DMI.grb	17680	6.3.2002 9:55	Buoys-20020306090100-FIMR.xml	47580
7.3.2002 16:28	Pressure-20020307060000-DMI.grb	17680	6.3.2002 11:17	Buoys-20020306110100-FIMR.xml	52570
8.3.2002 8:19	Pressure-20020308000000-DMI.grb	17680	7.3.2002 8:16	Buoys-20020307080100-FIMR.xml	45225
8.3.2002 21:26	Pressure-20020308180000-DMI.grb	17680	7.3.2002 16:30	Buoys-20020307160100-FIMR.xml	60025
9.3.2002 10:29	Pressure-20020309060000-DMI.grb	17680	7.3.2002 18:16	Buoys-20020307180100-FIMR.xml	64041
10.3.2002 8:19	Pressure-20020310000000-DMI.grb	17680	8.3.2002 8:18	Buoys-20020308080100-FIMR.xml	50547
10.3.2002 18:37	Pressure-20020310120000-DMI.grb	17680	8.3.2002 16:47	Buoys-20020308160100-FIMR.xml	64558
11.3.2002 12:37	Pressure-20020311060000-DMI.grb	17680	8.3.2002 21:25	Buoys-20020308210100-FIMR.xml	73283
12.3.2002 9:37	Pressure-20020312060000-DMI.grb	17680	9.3.2002 10:30	Buoys-20020309100100-FIMR.xml	52422
13.3.2002 8:30	Pressure-20020313000000-DMI.grb	17680	10.3.2002 8:18	Buoys-20020310080100-FIMR.xml	52569
14.3.2002 11:16	Pressure-20020314060000-DMI.grb	14344	10.3.2002 18:36	Buoys-20020310180100-FIMR.xml	57795
15.3.2002 12:16	Pressure-20020315060000-DMI.grb	17680	11.3.2002 12:41	Buoys-20020311120100-FIMR.xml	56043
16.3.2002 9:23	Pressure-20020316060000-DMI.grb	17680	11.3.2002 15:04	Buoys-20020311140100-FIMR.xml	64925
17.3.2002 10:20	Pressure-20020317060000-DMI.grb	17680	12.3.2002 9:35	Buoys-20020312090100-FIMR.xml	58126
18.3.2002 13:19	Pressure-20020318060000-DMI.grb	17680	13.3.2002 8:29	Buoys-20020313080100-FIMR.xml	51160
19.3.2002 10:09	Pressure-20020319060000-DMI.grb	17680	14.3.2002 11:15	Buoys-20020314110100-FIMR.xml	55724
20.3.2002 9:45	Pressure-20020320060000-DMI.grb	17680	14.3.2002 21:22	Buoys-20020314210100-FIMR.xml	77493
21.3.2002 10:59	Pressure-20020321060000-DMI.grb	17680	15.3.2002 12:19	Buoys-20020315110100-FIMR.xml	52201
			17.3.2002 10:17	Buoys-20020317100100-FIMR.xml	45661
			17.3.2002 17:10	Buoys-20020317170100-FIMR.xml	57651
			18.3.2002 13:20	Buoys-20020318130100-FIMR.xml	46694
			19.3.2002 10:10	Buoys-20020319090100-FIMR.xml	38071
			20.3.2002 9:45	Buoys-20020320090100-FIMR.xml	36491
			21.3.2002 11:02	Buoys-20020321100100-FIMR.xml	31140
			22.3.2002 10:46	Buoys-20020322100100-FIMR.xml	30510

Compression (bytes)

Compression (bytes)

	Without	With		Without	With
Number of files	25		Number of files	32	
Minimum file size	1105	1017	Minimum file size	30510	3966
Average file size	16884	15533	Average file size	54420	7075
Maximum file size	17680	16266	Maximum file size	81198	10556

Appendix 2. The user straw poll.

**R/V Aranda IWICOS demonstration
during FRAMZY-2002 in March 2002**

Questions to data and IWICOS System users.

Please, fill in every time new IWICOS data is received.

This straw poll will be used for the IWICOS System development.

Date and time (UTC):	
Location (lat./long.):	
Base:	Aranda
User:	
Data type:	SAR image name:
Data type:	Air pressure forecast: Forecast period:
Data type:	Wind forecast: Forecast period:
Data type:	Buoy data:
Data downloading time (minutes):	
Number of tries before downloading succeeded:	
Difficulties in receiving? Potential reasons for these (this)?:	
Quality of received data:	
Usability of received data:	
Comments, non-functionalities and how the IWICOS System could be developed better	
Other comments:	

Thank you for your trouble.

**R/V Aranda IWICOS demonstration
during FRAMZY-2002 in March 200**

FEEDBACK FORM

**ALL SYSTEM USERS MUST FILL THE FORM ONCE A WEEK OR AT
LEAST AFTER THE EXPERIMENT.**

This feedback will be used for the IWICOS System development.

TECHNICAL FUNCTIONALITY:

Have the ViewIce application functioned well? If not, what kind of problems have there been?

Have the data downloading functioned well? What kind of problems have you encountered?

- | |
|--|
| • Difficulties to connect in to the Iridium satellite |
| • Difficulties to connect in data downloading |
| • Difficulties to connect in to the web server |
| • Difficulties to download the data to the PC |

Forced to start the data downloading many times?

Have needed information been easy to find?

SYSTEM USE:

How often has the system been used? Who have the users been?

How may RADARSAT images have you downloaded?

Which areas the RADARSAT images have been covered?

Have you downloaded weather forecasts and how often?

Have you used buoy data?

BENEFITS:

Do you have examples of benefits using image data? When image data have effected to your decisions? Which especial images have been useful (image
--

names:)
Opinions about image interpretation? Have there been difficulties and should there also be an ice chart available?
Have the image data been fresh enough?
Have there been benefits combining image and weather data? Examples?
Have the needs of ARANDA been taken care of enough?

IDEAS FOR FURTHER DEVELOPMENT:

For data downloading
For information presentation
For collecting the information
Other ideas for development and comments
Are there any special things or functionalities the system is missing?

User's name:	
---------------------	--

Thank you for your trouble.

Integrated Weather, Sea Ice and Ocean Service System (IWICOS)

IWICOS DEMONSTRATION REPORT:

M.V. Arina Arctica demonstration June – September 2002

Author: Morten Lind (DMI)

Contract Number: IST-1999-11129

Danish Meteorological Institute
November 2002

CONSORTIUM PARTICIPANTS

Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI)
Lyngbyvej 100
DK-2100 Copenhagen, Denmark
Phone: +45 39157350
Fax: +45 39157390
E-mail: mli@dmi.dk

Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO)
Bustadvegur 9
IS-150 Reykjavik, Iceland
Phone: + 354 522 6000
Fax: + 354 522 6001
E-Mail: iwicos@vedur.is

INVESTIGATORS

DMI: Morten Lind, Lars Ørum Rasmussen
IMO: Halla Björg Baldursdóttir, Guðmundur Hafsteinsson, Björn Sævar Einarsson
and Anna Sigríður Arnadóttir

DEMONSTRATION PARTNER

Royal Arctic Line A/S
Grønlandshavnen
Postboks 8100
DK-9220 Aalborg
Telefon +45 99 30 32 34
Telefax +45 99 30 30 65

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Executive summary

The operational demonstration of the thick client 'Met-Ice-Ocean Viewer' (in short, the MIO Viewer) took place aboard the vessel Arina Arctica during two cruises. The first cruise covered the period of May 30th - July 12th 2002. The second cruise covered the period of August 20th - September 26th 2002. Arina Arctica is owned by Royal Arctic Line and operates on the east and west coast of Greenland. The vessel is a general cargo/container carrier which operates as a supplier for the largest communities primarily at the west coast of Greenland.

In this case, the IWICOS system has been demonstrated with particular emphasis on the End-user system, i.e. the Facade and the thick client (MIO Viewer). The MIO Viewer was fed with data from three producers during the demonstration: the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast, ECMWF (data available through DMI) and the Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO). DMI has been responsible for supporting the MIO Viewer, adjusting the user profile and has acted as a producer of numerical predictions of meteorological parameters and of sea ice analyses and satellite imagery. ECMWF has produced numerical predictions of oceanographic data and IMO has acted as a producer of textual weather forecasts for Icelandic forecast areas.

Altogether the user at the ship downloaded 185 data packages consisting of 11 satellite images, 11 ice analyses, 375 pressure forecasts, 375 wind forecasts, 300 wave forecasts (direction and height), 300 swell forecasts (direction and height) and 13 textual weather forecasts for Icelandic waters. The provision of numerical predictions has been regular, consisting of one daily broadcast. The provision of ice information and satellite data has been irregular and data is primarily from June and the beginning of July where high concentrations of ice were found around Cape Farewell. The provision of textual forecasts for Icelandic waters were limited to the periods where the vessel operated the route across the North Atlantic Ocean, back and forth from Denmark to Greenland.

Data provision was controlled by a predefined user profile which governs the facade data operations and the provision schedule. Data from numerical prediction models originally stored in GRIB format were converted to a client specific format through a set of facade operations at DMI. Ice analyses and satellite images were bundled in zip files. Textual forecasts in XML format were fetched directly from an IMO web server and bundled in zip files prior to provision.

The vast majority of data were automatically pushed to a central mail server and accessed by the user through an Inmarsat-B satellite connection. At some occasions, when fast access to ice conditions were required, the crew were informed of new data through an Inmarsat-C telex connection. Finally, data was presented to the user via the MIO Viewer.

In general, the IWICOS system and the MIO Viewer operated as planned. The user feedback was positive although some recommendations can be deduced from the users response. Based on the answers to the questionnaire and discussion with crew members, following issues should be addressed when considering future development of the system:

- Better integration between existing navigational equipment and the MIO Viewer should be considered. This includes a way of obtaining a GPS input from the existing GPS receiver and the possibility of transferring waypoint information from the basic navigational system to the MIO Viewer route module. However, no integration is desired between navigational maps and

weather/ocean information as it is the users point of view that such an integration would confuse more than it would ease the use of the system.

- Longer prognoses are desired for meteorological data which implies that data from models other than HIRLAM should be investigated in the future.
- From previous discussions with the users it is the authors point of view that not only the 'raw' numerical prediction output, but also derived products including visualisation of frontal systems and positions of low and high pressure zones – information which is found in more traditional weather maps are desired. In relation to this, a great challenge lies in the automation of producing such data.
- It is the authors point of view that more emphasis should be put on training of personnel concerning use of the client.

1 Background and Operational Area

The collaboration between DMI and Royal Arctic Line has been going on for many years and DMI provides conventional ice information to vessels from Royal Arctic Line operating Greenland waters. Throughout the IWICOS project, Royal Arctic Line has acted as a test partner regarding the development of the MIO Viewer presentation system and has been using and evaluating meteorological, oceanographic and sea ice data. Consequently, a vessel from Royal Arctic Line was a natural choice for an official demonstration of the IWICOS system.

The IWICOS demonstration aboard Arina Arctica was carried out during the normal operation schedule by Royal Arctic Line. Arina Arctica operates approximately five weeks at a time going back and forth between Aalborg, Denmark and the west coast of Greenland, see Figure 1. The vessel initially does a one week cruise in the Atlantic Ocean from Aalborg, Denmark to Nuuk, Greenland. Subsequently, the ship operates as feeder at the west coast of Greenland for approximately three weeks. Finally, the ship returns to Aalborg going back across the North Atlantic Ocean. The ship usually has port calls at six locations during the Atlantic cruise, including Reykjavik, Iceland. When operating as feeder along the west coast of Greenland the ship has port calls at eight locations going back and forth between Nuuk and northern locations respectively Nuuk and southern locations.

Figure 1: Operational area indicated by ship positions at various times during demonstration period.

2 Role of IWICOS partners

With the operational area being Greenland waters and the North Atlantic Ocean, including Icelandic waters, it was decided to demonstrate the interoperability within IWICOS including DMI and IMO in the demonstration. The partner specific roles were the following:

DMI installed the MIO Viewer application aboard the ship, trained users and supported the client during the demonstration. DMI delivered meteorological, oceanographic, sea ice information and satellite images to the ship. DMI hosted the necessary facade components.

IMO provided textual weather forecasts for Icelandic forecasts areas.

3 Description of the system

In Figure 2 is shown a schematic representation of the IWICOS system as it appears for the Arina Arctica demonstration. Data at producer level are stored in IWICOS exchange formats, like GRIB for numerical predictions, Shapefile for ice analyses and XML for textual weather forecasts.

Figure 2: The IWICOS system as it appears in the Arina Arctica demonstration.

At Facade level, data enters a data operation module which handles production of client tailored products through data rearrangement, bundling, format conversion and compression. Also, at Facade level a user profile is established as a set of configuration files which govern the data

operations and distribution to the client system. The profile is adjusted from time to time based on modified demands from the user. Profile adjustments is entirely based on mail correspondence between the user and personnel at DMI.

From the Facade level the data is pushed as mail to a central mail server according to a predefined schedule. The ship crew then pulls data from the mail server through an Inmarsat-B satellite connection. Finally, data can be displayed in the MIO Viewer application aboard the ship.

The mail system is the common way of transferring data within the Royal Arctic Line company. With the restrictions put up by the company concerning the communication system this mail solution was also chosen for the demonstration.

4 Data provision to Arina Arctica

Characteristics of the data products (temporal, spatial, thematic) were related to factors like operational area, satellite data availability, ice conditions, numerical model characteristics (both temporal and spatial), communication capabilities and requirements to the provision schedule.

4.1 Communication

All transfer of data to the ship went through an Inmarsat-B connection with a bandwidth of 9600 Baud. The vessel never operated north of 70° which is the guaranteed limit for reception using Inmarsat-B. Consequently, Inmarsat was considered to fulfil the requirements regarding data reception. All data were retrieved from a central mail server as mail attachments.

Table 1 reveals the statistics associated with the data communication. It should be pointed out that package sizes are somewhat smaller in size than the corresponding mail message size that contains the package attachment. Figure 3 shows the size and date of data received for the two cruises.

PACKAGE TYPE	TOTAL NO.	MIN. SIZE (KB)	MAX. (KB)	AVG. (KB)	TOTAL (KB)
Ice analyses	11	98	416	246	2706
Meteorology (wind, pressure)	75	25	27	26	1952
Oceanography (wave, swell)	75	9	19	13	958
Satellite images	7	22	248	130	911
Weather forecasts (textual)	13	7	7	7	95

Table 1: Data package sizes of data delivered during demonstration.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of size and date of data received at Arina Arctica.

The total amount of data delivered during the demonstration was 6622 kb which is on average 86 kb pr. day. However, as shown in Figure 3 a major part of the large-size data from ice analyses and satellite imagery is irregularly distributed in time.

4.2 Data provision schedule

Table 2 express data characteristics, and the provision schedule for data delivered to Arina Arctica during the demonstration.

PARAMETER	CATEGORY	PROGNOSES (HOURS)	PROVIDER	FREQUENCY
Mean Sea Level Pressure	Meteorology	12:24:36:48:60	DMI	1/day
Wind Speed (10 meter)	Meteorology	12:24:36:48:60	DMI	1/day
Wind Direction (10 meter)	Meteorology	12:24:36:48:60	DMI	1/day
Significant Wave Height	Oceanography	24:48:72:96	DMI	1/day
Mean Wave Direction	Oceanography	24:48:72:96	DMI	1/day
Significant Height of Primary Swell	Oceanography	24:48:72:96	DMI	1/day
Mean Direction of Primary Swell	Oceanography	24:48:72:96	DMI	1/day
Ice Analysis	Sea Ice	Observation	DMI	When available
NOAA sub-images	Satellite Imagery	Observation	DMI	When available
RADARSAT sub-images	Satellite Imagery	Observation	DMI	When available
Textual weather forecasts	Met/Ocean	Varying	DMI	2/day

Table 2: Data provision schedule during demonstration. Please note that data packages comprise several parameters and several prognoses.

4.3 Spatial data coverage

The forecast/prognosis area were at all times adjusted according to ship position. Overall, data from three generic forecast areas were accessible during the demonstration. Two areas were related to the meteorological and oceanographic numerical predictions. The eastern area was preferred when the vessel operated the Atlantic Ocean and the western area when the ship was operating as feeder at the Greenland west coast (see Figure 4 A and B). The third area was related to the textual forecasts from IMO (see Figure 4 C). Data for this area only had relevance while the ship was located within or in the circumference of the Icelandic forecast areas. For these data a typical period of usage would be 3-6 days.

Figure 4: A) Forecast area for numerical predictions when the ship was located in the North Atlantic Ocean. B) Forecast area for numerical predictions when the ship was operating as feeder at the Greenland west coast. C) Forecast areas for Icelandic textual forecasts.

Characteristics of all three areas are:

Area A (Eastern area):

- Extent:
$$\begin{array}{ccc} & 68 \text{ N} & \\ & \text{-----|-----} & \\ 70 \text{ W} & & 10 \text{ E} \\ & 45 \text{ N} & \end{array}$$
- Resolution/spacing: 150 km
- Grid size: 592

Area B (Western area):

- Extent:
$$\begin{array}{ccc} & 70 \text{ N} & \\ & \text{-----|-----} & \\ 100 \text{ W} & & 35 \text{ W} \\ & 40 \text{ N} & \end{array}$$
- Resolution/spacing: 150 km
- Grid size: 620

Area C (Icelandic forecast areas):

- Generic extent (bounding coordinates):
$$\begin{array}{ccc} & 70 \text{ N} & \\ & \text{-----|-----} & \\ 40 \text{ W} & & 0 \\ & 59 \text{ N} & \end{array}$$
- No. of individual forecast areas: 17 (8 outer areas and 9 inner banks). Only 10 areas were used in the demonstration.

4.4 Data in more detail

4.4.1 Origin

Table 3 gives an overview of the origin of the data that were provided to Arina Arctica during the demonstration.

PARAMETER	CATEGORY	ORIGIN
Mean Sea Level Pressure	Meteorology	HIRLAM-G* Numerical Prediction Model (DMI)
Wind Speed (10 meter)	Meteorology	HIRLAM-G Numerical Prediction Model (DMI)
Wind Direction (10 meter)	Meteorology	HIRLAM-G Numerical Prediction Model (DMI)
Significant Wave Height	Oceanography	ECMWF** Wave Model (ECMWF, UK)
Mean Wave Direction	Oceanography	ECMWF Wave Model (ECMWF, UK)
Significant Height of Primary Swell	Oceanography	ECMWF Wave Model (ECMWF, UK)
Mean Direction of Primary Swell	Oceanography	ECMWF Wave Model (ECMWF, UK)
Ice Analysis	Sea Ice	Ice Analysis (Ice Charting Division, DMI)
RADARSAT sub-images	Satellite Imagery	Tromsø, Gatineau and West Freugh receiving stations (Radarsat International)
NOAA sub-images	Satellite Imagery	Soenderstroem and Smidsbjerg receiving stations (DMI)
Textual weather forecasts	Met/Ocean	Shipping Forecast (IMO)

Table 3: Origin of data provided during demonstration.

*HIRLAM is an acronym for ‘High Resolution Limited Area Model’ and ‘G’ specifies the model area. The HIRLAM model is run at a NEC-SX-4/SX-6 supercomputer located at DMI.

**ECMWF is an acronym for ‘European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecast’ located in Reading, UK.

4.4.2 Meteorological data (numerical predictions)

Meteorological data consisted of the parameters, *mean sea level pressure* and *10 meter wind speed/wind direction*. The parametric values were based on the morning analysis at 06 UTC from the DMI HIRLAM–G numerical prediction model. The HIRLAM-G model has an original grid size of 202*190 data points and a resolution of 0.45°. The maximum forecast length is +60h.

All in all, 375 prognoses of pressure and wind were retrieved by the ship during demonstration. Of these, 130 prognoses covered the eastern area (North Atlantic Ocean) and the remaining 245 covered the western area (see Figure 4).

4.4.3 Oceanographic data (numerical predictions)

Numerically modelled oceanographic data consisted of the parameters *significant wave height*, *mean wave direction*, *significant height of primary swell* and *mean direction of primary swell*. The

parametric values were based on the analysis at 12 UTC from the ECMWF-WAM (wave model). The ECMWF-WAM has an original grid size of 421*171 data points and a resolution of 0.25°. The maximum forecast is +120h.

The ship crew required that all numerical predictions were provided in the morning. With only the 12 UTC analysis available, this implied that oceanographic data would already have an age of app. 20 hours before reaching the ship.

A total of 300 prognoses of oceanographic parameters were retrieved by the ship. Of these, 100 covered the eastern area, whereas 200 covered the western area.

4.4.4 Weather forecasts (Icelandic areas)

The textual forecasts are produced at the Icelandic Meteorological Office several times a day. Data which are retrieved twice a day consist of a morning forecast which is due app. 07 UTC and an evening forecast which is due app. 20 UTC. The textual forecasts apply to individual forecast areas of which there are 17 in total. For the IWICOS demonstration only the 10 southernmost areas are used. The ship normally navigates a route south of Iceland and data from the northernmost areas are consequently superfluous.

Data for the individual area consist of a textual weather forecast including information on wind speed, -direction, precipitation and an indication of the expected maximum wind speed. Possible warnings related to weather conditions are furthermore displayed. A synopsis of the weather situation for the whole region is provided as well.

During the demonstration 13 forecast packages were retrieved by the ship. This means that a total of 130 forecasts were available for further investigation.

4.4.5 Sea ice analyses

A sea ice analysis actually consists of two data sets in the same package delivery:

- a) polygonal features which for a given area describes the various sea ice parameters, i.e. concentration, stage of development and floe size.
- b) point features which for a local point or very limited area represents the occurrence of ice bergs, growlers, belts, etc.

Sea ice analyses are produced at DMI and is based on human interpretation of satellite imagery, primarily RADARSAT and secondly NOAA AVHRR and DMSP SSM/I. The ice analysis is provided to the ship ad hoc determined by the ice situation. During the demonstration period, especially June and first part of July were critical in terms of ice propagation and distribution. Thus, substantial areas of sea ice of high concentrations were coinciding with the operational area of Arina Arctica. Consequently, the transfer of ice analyses to the ship was most abundant in this period.

A total of 11 analyses were retrieved by the ship. All analyses covered the area around Cape Farewell, south-eastern and south-western Greenland, see Figure 5.

Figure 5: An ice situation around Cape Farewell in medio June.

4.4.6 Satellite imagery

Alongside the provision of ice analyses, a number of sub-images from RADARSAT and NOAA were distributed to the ship. The combined effect of having the source information together with the interpreted ice analyses product is often preferable in terms of gaining optimum information on ice conditions.

During demonstration a total of 11 sub-images were provided. Nine were RADARSAT images provided as imagine files. Two were NOAA images - one in the imagine format and one in the MrSID wavelet compressed image format.

5 Detailed description of the system

In the following a detailed description of the IWICOS system is given. Emphasis will be put on the production, Facade and client components as these have been the primary subject to demonstrate in the Arina Arctica situation.

5.1 Producer servers

As previously mentioned the producer level consisted of three server sites – one at DMI, one at ECMWF and one at IMO, see Figure 6.

Figure 6: The three production sites that were part of the demonstration.

At the DMI, numerical predictions for the HIRLAM-G area are produced four times a day and stored in GRIB format. Satellite image data are acquired from a number of sources (see Table 3), processed and stored at DMI.

Based on interpretation of satellite imagery, ice analyses are produced in an integrated GIS and image analysis system. At producer level the ice analyses are stored in the Arc&INFO coverage format.

At ECMWF oceanographic wave model data for the area of interest are produced once a day and is made available for DMI as part of the co-operation agreement between ECMWF and member countries. Data from the ECMWF-WAM are stored in GRIB format analogously to the predictions from HIRLAM.

At IMO the textual weather forecasts are produced several times a day in the XML format. Twice a day, data for 10 forecast areas were retrieved from the IMO server.

5.2 Facade

The Facade contained two main modules which were closely integrated, the 'Data Operation Module' and the 'Profile Module' The Data Operation Module takes care of all data related manipulation activities, see Figure 7.

Figure 7: A schematic representation of the Facade data operation module.

The second module, the profile module, controls the data operation module through a set of profile configuration files, see Figure 8.

Figure 8: The Facade profile configuration module.

Through this set of files the user profile was adjusted from time to time based on modified user requests. The configuration has to be set up manually each time the user modified the demands. However, during the demonstration the modified user requests was mainly related to switching between forecast areas and turning on and off parts of the data provision like, for example, Icelandic forecasts. The work load involved in these tasks was therefore small.

5.3 Stand-alone client – the MIO Viewer

The MIO Viewer was used for display of the assemblage of met-ice-ocean data described above. Examples of data visualisation is given in Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Figure 9: MIO Viewer presentation example for the western area for the 19th of June. MSL pressure shown as red isobars; wind barbs shown in black; wave height shown as magenta height indications; wave direction shown as magenta arrows; an ice analysis for Cape Farewell shown in colour code. A fictive route is shown as yellow and GPS/waypoint information is presented in the open dialog.

Figure 10: MIO Viewer presentation example for part of the eastern area for the 26th of August. MSL pressure shown as red isobars; wind barbs shown in black; swell height shown as magenta height indications; swell direction shown as magenta vectors; a textual forecast for an Icelandic area is shown in the open dialog; a NOAA sub-image in the MrSID format is shown for the area around Tasilaq; the actual route of Arina Arctica is shown in blue.

Once data was received at the ship these were put into a local data directory from where MIO Viewer could access data and subsequently process and display the products (for a detailed description of MIO Viewer architecture and presentation capabilities, please see Extended System Report, 2002).

6 User comments

Aboard the ship mainly one person has been operating the MIO Viewer. He was given several introductions to the client during the development phase. He has been investigating the system using the accompanying guide and has tried out a broad variety of functionalities. Other personnel from Royal Arctic Line has been using the system from time to time.

Additionally, the MIO Viewer was installed at the Ice Patrol, Narsarsuaq, Greenland in June 2002. Their use of the system does not entirely correspond to the way it is used aboard a vessel. At the Ice Patrol the personnel uses the client for visualisation of meteorological and oceanographic data as a support tool when informing vessels of weather and ocean conditions.

In terms of communication, the Ice Patrol are not subject to the same bandwidth limitations as the vessel and therefore can use the satellite imagery visualisation part more extensively. Thus, daily NOAA scenes are visualised in the MIO Viewer together with ice analyses from DMI for interpretation of ice conditions. At the Ice Patrol the route module is rarely used and for obvious reasons the GPS module is never used.

The following conclusions and recommendations concerning the IWICOS system and in particular the MIO Viewer is primarily based on discussions with Royal Arctic Line's personnel and personnel at the Greenland Ice Patrol and their answers to the evaluation questionnaire, see appendix.

The overall user feedback regarding the system performance was positive. From the developers point of view most of the IWICOS system components which was tried out during this demonstration has operated satisfactory. However, minor problems on the producer's side have been identified. These were related to the automatic production of IMO textual forecast files, where files at some occasions were not updated at the web server. This was corrected towards the end of the demonstration. In a few cases the DMI Facade did not deliver oceanographic and meteorological numerical predictions due to server problems.

7 Recommendations regarding the IWICOS system

The implementation of the IWICOS system during this demonstration differed somewhat from the implementation that was used for the Aranda demonstration (see R/V Aranda Demonstration During the Fram Strait Expedition in March 2002'). In the Aranda demonstration the user profile could be edited through a profile user interface in a web browser aboard the ship and thus, changes for facade operations was automatically invoked at the provider site. In the Arina Arctica demonstration the profile adjustments were invoked manually on the provider side and were based on mail correspondence between the ship crew and DMI personnel. With no internet access, the ship has to rely on this form of correspondence when changes for products were required. However, the mail correspondence did not present any problems for the user. Other options for automating the profile adjustments when dealing with pure mail correspondence could be investigated in future development projects.

Other recommendations that would be worth considering in the future development of the IWICOS system would be:

- Better integration between existing navigational equipment and the MIO Viewer should be considered. This includes a way of obtaining a GPS input from the existing GPS receiver and the possibility of transferring waypoint information from the basic Maris navigational system to the MIO Viewer route module. However, no integration is desired between navigational maps and weather/ocean information as it is the users point of view, that such an integration would confuse more that it would ease the use of the system.

- Longer prognoses are desired for meteorological data which implies that data from models other than HIRLAM should be investigated in the future.
- From previous conversations with the users it is the authors point of view that not only the 'raw' numerical prediction output, but also derived products including visualisation of frontal systems and positions of low and high pressure zones – information which is found in more traditional weather maps are desired. In relation to this a great challenge lies in the automation of producing such data.
- It is the authors point of view that more emphasis should be put on training of personnel concerning use of the client.

8 Conclusion

The demonstration aboard the vessel Arina Arctica from Royal Arctic Line was carried out during two cruises in the period of June – September 2002. The demonstration was very much focussed on the production process and the IWICOS end-user system, i.e. the Facade and client components. Following major issues were demonstrated:

- Data production leading to a varied product assemblage
- Facade data operations including bundling, conversion, compression, etc.
- Data provision
- Communication
- Client performance including processing, presentation, GPS and route modules

The Arina Arctica demonstration complements very well the demonstration aboard Aranda. The two demonstrations have focussed on different parts of the IWICOS system. The Aranda demonstration was related to a research field experiment within a reasonably small area, whereas the Arina Arctica demonstration was related to commercial cargo traffic comprising a reasonably large area. In the Aranda demonstration focus was very much on the whole IWICOS service chain including the Broker and metadata part, whereas in the Arina Arctica demonstration focus was on the end-user system with particular emphasis on the stand alone client performance.

Two IWICOS partners participated in the demonstration and their responsibility areas were as follows:

- DMI was a producer of numerical predictions of meteorological and oceanographic data, ice analysis and satellite imagery.
- DMI hosted the Facade and maintained the user profile.
- IMO was a producer of textual weather forecasts and made these available in XML format.

Data was routed through the Facade data operation module and made available to the client in specially designed packages and client specific formats. Data was transferred from a common mail server to the ship using an Inmarsat 9600 Baud connection.

Altogether, the ship downloaded 185 data packages consisting of:

- 375 meteorological prognoses (wind and pressure)
- 300 oceanographic prognoses (wave and swell)
- 130 textual weather forecasts

- 11 ice analyses
- 11 satellite images

Downloaded products were displayed in the Met-Ice-Ocean Viewer and presented in conjunction with GPS and route related information.

The overall user response was positive although some recommendations could be deduced from the questionnaire and from interviews with the ship crew. Future development of the system should address issues like better integration of client with existing navigational equipment, extended products including frontal zones and positions on high and low pressure zones, easier adjustment of user profile and more training of users.

Appendix 1

MIO Viewer Evaluation

Users response from demonstrations

Vessel: Arina Arctica
Responder: The captain

Category: Users

How many persons use MIO Viewer on a daily basis ?

Only I have been using the system during the last year – a period where the system has been located aboard the vessel Kista Arctica and this vessel Arina Arctica. At Kista Arctica the system was used to some extent by another captain and some navigators. The other captains operating Arina Arctica has been introduced to the system, but for different reasons have not been interested in using it.

How varied is the use of MIO Viewer (several times a day, daily, weekly) ?

From one to several times a day depending if the vessel is operating in ice infested areas and receiving RADARSAT images.

For the Atlantic cruises I use the system at least once every morning to check weather information and at many occasions I use the system later the same day as well.

Which are the users background ?

All are navigators.

Other comments ?

It's a bit difficult to fill out such a questionnaire in writing. Several issues are hard to explain and could be better illustrated directly at the screen.

Category: Data

Which data do you use the most ?

The meteorological data.

How often do you use these data ?

On a daily basis.

Do you find the data availability sufficient ?

Have earlier discussed possible prognoses lasting up till 96, maybe 120 hours, but then data file sizes would be too large. If we removed 36 hours it we could apply 96 and 120 hours. I use the 12 hour prognosis as the analysis, but 36 isn't used in particular.

Has the data quality been satisfactory – if not, which data has then had non-satisfactory quality and in what situations ?

Yes the quality has been sufficient.

Is there data which isn't used at all – if so, which ?

Yes, at the moment the temperature data is not used. We only use those during the period from Nov/Dec – April in respect to the risk of icing.

Met: only represented as wind barbs, isobars, isotherms..

Ocean: similarly representation as to meteorological data.

Are there desires for other types of data ?

No not for the moment.

Are prognoses long enough ?

As stated earlier I would like to have 96 and 120 hour prognoses provided that file sizes are kept reasonable.

Is the temporal resolution of prognoses satisfactory ?

Yes

Are there particular prognoses which you prefer ?

Yes, 24 and 48 hours are used the most.

Is the spatial extent of met/ocean fields satisfactory ?

Yes it is and now where we are able to ask for varied extends it is very satisfactory.

Is the spatial resolution of met/ocean data satisfactory ?

Yes

Other Comments ?

Category: User interface and functionality

Is the user interface (buttons, menus, etc.) intuitive and easy to use ?

Yes, indeed.

Are there particular user interface components which are difficult to understand ?

No

Have you experienced functionality that doesn't work ?

No

Are there any functionality or user interface components which needs to be changed before you would use it ?

No

Are there functionality which you don't use at all ?

It is not every day we use all functionality

Do you have desires for faster access to certain functionality ?

No

Are there functionality which you have been particularly keen on ?

Yes, the route editor.

Do you have suggestions for new functionality which could be useful ?

Not for the moment, no.

Category: Presentation

Do you combine data in ice chart/prognosis windows and if so, which ?

Normally, no. For the sake of clarity the charts are presented individually

Have you used the multi prognoses windows – if so, in what situations ?

We use it every day for route planning and presentation of forecasts.

Are there methods for presenting data which currently is non-appropriate and could be done otherwise ?

No, not as far as I can see.

Other comments ?

Category: The Route Module

Have the digitalisation of routes by mouse been used ?

Yes, together with the 'position' functionality. We apply positions, draw routes using mouse, save route files and remove positions. This I find is a fast and easy method.

Have the option for entering routes using the keyboard been used ?

Yes, a few times, but I find it difficult to use.

Have the route editing module been used ?

Yes, often and it is very easy to use.

Have you experienced problems with the route module – entering coordinates, editing or other ?

See answers above.

Would it be useful to transfer the route from Maris to MIO Viewer in digital form ?

Well, yes and no; there might be too many waypoints entering the system, so it would be confusable.

Is the route module satisfactory ?

Yes

Other comments ?

Category: The GPS Module

Have the GPS module been used – if so, in what situations ?

We use the GPS module all the time.

Which update frequency has been used ?

Most of the time 300 sec, but likewise 60 sec.

Has the waypoint information been used for anything ?

Yes, to check.

Have the waypoint ETA estimations been used ?

Yes

Assuming yes - have the waypoint ETA estimations been based on both manual and GPS speed ?

Manual speed has only been used for checking purposes, otherwise the GPS speed has been used.

Has the estimate of vessel position according to time of prognosis been used ?

Yes, to compare prognoses with the actual situation.

Has the 'invert route' function been used ?

No, since we never go back the same route we went out.

Have you used the option for selecting a particular waypoint ?

No, not really since we follow the route.

Have you used the option 'Consecutive' for waypoint snapping ?

We haven't found use for it, by I have tried it out and it works fine.

Other comments ?

It is annoying that the actual GPS position always is located at the centre of the window, especially when zooming is performed and when the route is planned and printed.

***Authors note:** Unfortunately the user has not been aware that options already are available for changing the auto-updating focus area and turning on and off this feature.

Category: Icelandic forecasts

Have you had benefits from using the Icelandic forecasts ?

No we have not

Has the data availability been sufficient (twice a day) ?

The data is outdated once we receive it and this only makes it useful as analyses

***Authors note:** Outdated data was caused by production problems at IMO

Have you used both forecasts or did you prefer the morning or evening forecast ?

Both have been used

Did data match the real world (sufficient quality) ?

Yes, I would say so

Is the presentation method satisfactory ?

If we have had the monitor at the bridge all the time the method would be good – however, since we have to print the forecast and since only the active view is printed, it is of no use.

***Authors note:** The client system was located in a cabin at the deck below and therefore physically separated from the bridge. The reason for this choice of location was a combination of space limitations at the bridge and requirements for a separate GPS connectivity which was easier reached from this cabin.

The visual representation is disturbed due to area labels in the forecasts areas – they would have to be removed. Colours are okay, but no text labels should be included.

Do you think it would be beneficial to extend the module to include forecasts areas for the coast of Greenland ?

No I don't think so

Other comments ?

It is difficult to write pros and cons concerning the presentation – its much easier to show directly at the monitor.

Category: Data Management

Have you used the possibility to generate all met/ocean products at once to save time when products are supposed to be presented operationally ?

No, cause when we work with these data the time is not that crucial – accuracy is more important.

Do you erase products from the hard disc from time to time ?

No

Do you, from time to time, move outdated data from working directory to archive ?

Yes, always when new data arrive I clean up the working directory and moves outdated data to archive.

Other comments ?

Category: Communication

Does the data transmission work properly ?

Almost 100% - the only failure we have experienced is related to the oceanographic data. 10 – 15 times we did not receive these during the one year period I have used the system.

Does data have a reasonably limited size ?

Yes, I think so.

Other comments ?

Category: General remarks

Do you have suggestions concerning how MIO Viewer in a beneficial way could be integrated with the basic navigational equipment like Maris or GPS ?

In relation to the existing equipment aboard RAL vessels, I don't think it would be worth while spending money on this, maybe because we are somewhat conservative. I would like the ice- and weather information separately and not together with navigational maps. I think this would be confusing.

Do you have suggestions to new functionality within MIO Viewer ?

No, I think I got the stuff I need for effectively navigating the ship and I can't think of any new functionality which could be useful. During the last five years we have got all we wanted.

Other comments ?

For several years I have been following and participating in the development of MIO Viewer and I must state that now I have a product which is easy to use, fast and very well organised. I can't imagine what could possibly be added to improve it, but other persons might be able to do that.

The captain at M/S Arina Arctica

DRAFT 12 November 2002

Integrated Weather, Sea Ice and Ocean Service System (IWICOS)

IWICOS DEMONSTRATION REPORT:

Thick and thin IWICOS clients demonstrated at the Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition 4-7 September 2002

Authors: Halla Björg Baldursdóttir, Guðmundur Hafsteinsson

Contract Number: IST-1999-11129

**Icelandic Meteorological Office
November 2002**

Icelandic meteorological Office (IMO) Bustadavegur 9, IS-150 Reykjavik, Iceland Phone: +354 522 6000 Fax: +354 522 6001 E-mail: halla@vedur.is	Radiomidun hf. Grandagardur 9, IS-101 Reykjavik, Iceland Phone: +354 511 1010 Fax: +354 511 1020 E-mail: kgisla@eyki.is
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INVESTIGATORS IMO: Halla Björg Baldursdóttir, Björn Sævar Einarsson, Guðmundur Hafsteinsson Radiomidun: Kristján Gíslason, Cecilia Magnúsdóttir University of Iceland: Ingibjörg Jónsdóttir

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Executive summary

IMO and Radiomidun demonstrated their thin and thick IWICOS clients at the Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition in Smárinn, Kópavogur, 4-7 September 2002. Captains and ship owners were selected for the demonstration and afterwards they were asked about their opinion of the clients, the products and how they would like to access them. 95 answers were obtained. The answers were generally very positive. The most wanted product was definitely the wave forecast, captains on small boats were most interested in accessing the products on a web page while captains on bigger ships did also want to have the products sent on board the ship. Many people said that they might be willing to pay a reasonable amount for such a service but very few were willing to say how much.

Exhibition

Iceland is heavily depended on its fishing industry and 72% of the country's export comes from fish or fish related products, making this exhibition vital not only to the Icelanders but to any international company looking to enter this buoyant market.

Iceland ranks no 13 on the FAO World Catch list with 1.7 million tonnes caught fish. Having maintained close control of its fish stocks and carefully managed the activity of its vessels, Iceland is one of the few countries within Europe, which will not be suffering from the recent EU catch restrictions. It has often been suggested that the Icelandic Fleet represents state of the art of the fisheries technology. Skippers and owners update and modernise their fleets on a regular basis providing exhibitors at the Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition an ideal opportunity to meet and discuss new requirements.

The Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition has been running every three years since 1984 and moved in 1999 to a new and larger venue in Kópavogur. The show has through the years proved to be a major success with both exhibitors and visitors. The show has on every occasion grown in both size and numbers, and Icelandic Fisheries 2002 could claim

- More than 13000 m² of net exhibition space in three houses and additional 600 m² outdoors
- Almost 800 exhibiting companies from 37 countries
- Increase in visitor numbers by more than 20% to 16.993 from 42 countries.

Covering every aspect of the commercial fishing industry from catching, locating, processing, packaging to marketing of the final product, Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition is the considered as one of the four biggest fisheries exhibitions in the world.

The Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition is organised by Nexus Media Limited - which is a wholly owned subsidiary of Highbury House plc. - in cooperation with Icelandic marketing companies. Nexus has a current portfolio of over 260 business, consumer and specialist titles, books and directories, plus 62 exhibitions and 15 awards evenings.

Nexus are also publishers of World Fishing Magazine, now in its 49th year of publication.

More information on The Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition can be found on the webpage www.icefish.is

Clients

The biggest group of users of met-ice-ocean information in Icelandic waters are the fishermen. They can roughly be divided in two groups:

- Small boat owners, operating near the coast, often within range of mobile phones and arriving to the harbour daily.
- Captains/owners of bigger and better equipped vessels operating far from the coast for longer periods, out of range of mobile phones.

These two groups have similar needs for information but their possibilities to access data are quite different. Many small boat owners use the Internet most of the time while the captains of the bigger ships have to rely on satellite communication. It is therefore natural to develop two clients, thick and thin, to fulfil the needs of Icelandic fishermen for met-ice-ocean information.

The following products were demonstrated at the exhibition:

- Graphical interface to traditional text forecast where forecasting areas are coloured by maximum windspeed
 - Gives a quick overview over the weather situation
 - Some times the coloured area might be sufficient
- Ocean wave forecast maps, significant wave height, mean wave direction and mean wave period
 - Useful for all kind of vessels at all distances from the coast to avoid dangerous situations
- Ice accretion forecast, colour code used to indicate rate of icing
 - Three icing classes shown: Moderate - Heavy - Extreme
 - Useful to vessels operating in areas where there can be risk for icing
- Forecasting diagrams (meteograms)
 - Show local weather forecasts for coastal stations as time series
 - Useful for vessels operating close to the coast, mainly small boats
- Sea ice maps
 - Show ice edge and concentration
 - Useful for vessels operating near the ice edge or in the ice

The thin client is developed at IMO as a web site where as many as possible of the products needed by the seafarers will be made available. The target user group is mainly small boat owners and other seafarers operating relatively close to the coast. A strong emphasis is placed on avoiding "heavy stuff" in order to make it possible to use mobile phones (GSM/GPRS) to access the web and download the products. The client will also be used at home before sailing and by the seamen's families while they are out at sea.

The thick client is developed by Radiomidun and has been given the name Birtir (The Viewer). The software is installed on a PC onboard the ship. The target user group is captains of larger ships, out of reach for domestic communication. Several communication possibilities, such as Inmarsat Mini M, Iridium and Emsat can be used and the data is sent to the boat as an email attachment. The selection of met-ice-ocean products which will be made available through Birtir will be mainly the same as for the thin client but a range of other products will also be offered.

Figure 1 Screen captures from the two clients. Top left is the weather forecast with coloured forecasting areas according to maximum forecasted wind speed. Top right is a forecasting diagram for a station off the south coast of Iceland. Middle left is an ocean wave forecast map. Middle right is an icing forecast map. Bottom left is a sea ice map displayed as an overlay on a satellite image. All these products are shown as displayed by the thin client.

Bottom right is an image taken from the thick client Birtir. It shows the weather forecast for the high seas areas, coloured according to maximum forecasted wind speed.

Implementation

The two IWICOS clients developed by IMO and Radiomidun were demonstrated at Radiomidun's booth at the exhibition. The clients were installed on four computers and one of them was connected to an overhead projector.

A user oriented glossy brochure (see next chapter) had been prepared and was distributed to people who showed interest in the project.

All visitors of the exhibition were marked with a badge which indicated their relation to the fisheries. The target group for the demonstration was mainly captains of small and large fishing vessels. People marked as "Captain/Owner" were therefore picked out from the crowd and asked to participate in the demonstration. They received the brochure and after the demonstration they were asked a few questions about the products, the clients and how they would probably use them. The answers were registered on the questionnaire by the questioner.

The demonstration was carried out by five persons, three from IMO, one from Radiomidun and one from the University of Iceland. At least two were present all the time while the exhibition was open.

The captains showed a general interest in the demonstration and were pleased to see that research and development work was going on to improve the marine weather services. Very few declined to answer the questions. In the whole 95 captains/owners were interviewed and most of them gave answers to all the questions on the questionnaire.

To keep the questionnaire as simple and short as possible it was not asked explicitly about the size of the vessel. Sometimes however the questioner noted that the answers were given by a small boat captain/owner. These answers were also counted separately but they are also included in the whole sample. But it is very likely that some answers from small boat owners were not marked as such.

It should be noted that these interviews must be considered as an informal user survey. The answers may be biased in several ways and not strictly significant from a statistical point of view. It could for example be mentioned that one of the questioners had been a meteorology teacher for some of the younger captains and they might have wanted to please him.

Brochure

The following brochure which is supposed to be printed in A4 on both sides and folded into three was handed out to the persons that participated in the demonstration.

IWICOS project

The IWICOS project is a 3-year research and development project supported by the European Commission's Information Society Technologies Programme.

The objective of IWICOS is to develop a prototype marine information system that will provide end-users with a single-entry access to meteorological, sea ice and oceanographic data and products in an electronic form for:

- National ice and weather services
- Shipping companies and sea traffic administration
- Picking vessels and other ships operating in harsh climate
- Icebreaker captains and pilots of ships
- Oil companies and offshore industry
- Climate research, media, education and others

IWICOS products

Examples on IWICOS products:

- Text forecasts, possibly combined with explanatory maps
- Numerical weather forecasts presented on maps (wind, temperature, pressure, ice accretion etc.)
- Ice charts based on satellite images, reconnaissance flights and/or information from ships
- Numerical wave forecasts and other information on sea state, presented on maps

IWICOS in Iceland

Icelandic fishermen are the main target group for IWICOS in Iceland. The most important product is the weather forecast and warnings. A map will be added to the traditional weather forecast where the forecasting areas are colored according to expected maximum wind speed (see front page). New products are under development, i.e. wave forecasts, ice accretion forecast, sea ice charts. Data will be disseminated in two ways, with specially designed software on board the ships and on web pages.

IWICOS partners

	Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center Bergen
	Finnish Institute of Marine Research Helsinki
	Technical Research Centre of Finland Espoo
	Danish Meteorological Institute Copenhagen
	Danish Center for Remote Sensing Lyngby
	Icelandic Meteorological Office Reykjavik

Subcontractor to the Icelandic Meteorological Office is Radiamidun ehf. The project is supported by the University of Iceland.

IWICOS websites

Further information about IWICOS can be found by looking at the project web sites:

<http://www.nersc.no/~iwicos>
<http://www.vadur.is/iwicos>

ISSUE: 14. september 2002. English version: November 2002.

IWICOS

Integrated Weather, Sea Ice and Ocean Service System

Subanskrifing: NA 15-20 m/s norðantil og östurla eða til en 20-25 m/s norðantil og rigring. NA 18-23 m/s östlig og rigring. N 8-13 m/s vesturla undir morgun.

Icelandic Fisheries Exhibition
September 2002

IWICOS in a nutshell

Sea forecast from the Icelandic Meteorological Office

Forecasting diagram from the Icelandic Meteorological Office

Ice accretion forecast from the Icelandic Meteorological Office

Wave chart combined with a numerical wave forecast from the Danish Meteorological Office

Ice chart from the University of Iceland

Metadata is located on a server and contains information on existing data in IWICOS. Service providers and users can get information on data availability in certain areas at certain dates by communicating with the server. Data is delivered in a standardised format and can be presented both by common tools on the Interact and also by specially designed software onboard the ships. IMO's website, MaxSea and Radiamidun's new service bank are a few examples on presentation tools.

Questionnaire

- 1) How satisfied are you with the presentation of the weather forecast (textual forecast with indicated maximum wind speed on the forecast areas)?
 - a) 1 2 3 4 5 (very satisfied)
 - b) If negative answer, which are the main shortcomings?
- 2) What else did you find of most interest?
 - a) Wave forecast
 - b) Sea-ice information
 - c) Point forecasts (meteogram)
 - d) Ice accretion forecast
- 3) Would you like to have this information sent to you aboard the ship?
 - a) Yes, what could be the monthly price for such information service?
_____ kr.
 - b) No. Why not?
- 4) Would you use this page on the Web?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No. Why not?
- 5) Would it be most useful for you to view this information on the Web or to have it sent to you aboard the ship?
 - a) The Web
 - b) The ship
 - c) Both

Results

As mentioned earlier 95 answers to the questionnaire were collected from "Captains/Owners" at the exhibition. Most of them gave answers to all the questions. There was not asked explicitly about the size of the ship but in 18 cases it was noted that the answers were given by a small boat owner. These 18 can be used to study the opinions of small boat owners and compare them to the whole sample even if this may not be statically significant and even if there most certainly were more small boat owners in the sample. In the bar charts following each question blue bars are used for the whole sample but red bars for the smaller sample of 18 small boat owners.

- 1) *How satisfied are you with the presentation of the weather forecast (textual forecast with indicated maximum wind speed on the forecast areas)?*
 a) 1 2 3 4 5 (very satisfied)
 b) *If negative answer, which are the main shortcomings?*

The bar charts following the first question show clearly that a big majority of the captains did like the graphical interface to the text forecasts, most of them said that they were very satisfied or satisfied. No significant difference can be seen between the small boat owners and the whole sample.

Rather few mentioned any shortcomings but most of them said that they would like to have access to weather charts. Some mentioned isobars and fronts (like the well known weather charts from Bracknell), other were interested in animations.

The score used to evaluate the answers given to the second question needs some clarification. The captains could mention as many products as they wanted and they could prioritise them with numbers from 1 to 4. This made the counting of answers more difficult. The problem was solved by defining a scoring rule. A product which was mentioned and not given a priority scored one point. If more than one product was mentioned and given a priority order a higher score was given. Example: Three products mentioned, product a) with highest priority, then b) and c) lowest priority. This would give three points to product a), two points to b) and one point to c). This is the reason why the most popular product, the wave forecast, obtained more than 95 points.

These bar charts show very clearly that Icelandic captains consider the wave forecast to be the most important of these products. It was mentioned in almost every answer and often given the highest priority. Sea ice charts seem to be of little interest for small boat owners since they would normally only try to avoid any ice. Some captains operating from the south and east coast of Iceland mentioned that sea ice and ice accretion was usually not a problem in their area.

Answers to the third question show that the captains are generally interested in having the information sent to the ship. Three mentioned that they would rather "pull" the

information from the system than have it "pushed". The 18 small boat owners show nevertheless a quite different picture. The reason given for a negative answer was usually lack of equipment or communications.

It was very difficult to get a definite answer to the question on the monthly amount to pay for such services. The majority gave no answer but a few gave a subjective answer as "as little as possible" or "a fair amount". Very few were willing to give any number but when it happened 5000 IKR (~60€) or even more was mentioned.

- 4) *Would you use this page on the Web?*
 a) *Yes*
 b) *No. Why not?*

Almost everybody showed interest in having these products accessible on the web. The very few who gave a negative answer said that they didn't have a computer or could listen to everything on the radio. One thought that the maps would be too heavy for his slow modem.

The last question where the captains were asked which delivery method would be most useful for them gives three almost equal groups which favour the web, transmission to the ship and both methods. Here again, not unexpected, the 18 small boat owners show quite different opinion. They prefer to rely on the web only as their technical possibilities to receive information onboard the ship are rather primitive.

- 5) *Would it be most useful for you to view this information on the Web or to have it sent to you aboard the ship?*
- a) *The Web*
 - b) *The ship*
 - c) *Both*

As an overall view one can say that the captains asked showed a general interest in the demonstrated clients and products. Very few negative comments were heard. The answers support our previous assumption that the two clients, the thick and the thin, are needed to deliver the IWICOS products and other products which will be developed in the future to Icelandic fishermen. The reason for this is rather technical and economical rather than based on different needs.

SEA-ICE MONITORING IN ICELANDIC WATERS

By Ingibjörg Jónsdóttir, Ríkharður Friðrik Friðriksson and Katrín Hólm Hauksdóttir.
Science Institute, University of Iceland.

Definition

During the spring and summer of 2002, the Science Institute at the University of Iceland (UofI) carried out a sea-ice monitoring project in Icelandic waters. The purpose of the project was to evaluate the possibility of mapping the sea-ice around Iceland daily using only Quikscat and NOAA AVHRR satellite images, to interview users of sea-ice information in order to find out what kind of information is needed; when and how often, and finally to test means of sending the ice charts to users at sea. This short report emphasises the main results, but a more detailed report will be published soon.

Background

Previously in the IWICOS project, a user survey was conducted by *Gallup* where captains of fishing vessels were asked various questions on the current use and need for weather, sea-ice and ocean information. One of the limitations to that survey was the fact that captains were in some cases asked to comment on services and data that they were not familiar with or have not as yet been provided. Although this can be of use when listing main priorities in future development, the results do not tell the whole story. This was, for example, the case when captains were asked about their interest in using the internet. The overall response was rather negative, although in a different and a more open question the users described the qualities of the internet when commenting on their ideal media. Another restriction of the *Gallup* survey, when focusing on regular sea-ice services, was the high proportion of answers from captains on small vessels that do only need sea-ice information when the ice is very close to the coast. Larger ships, such as shrimp trawlers, need information about areas farther from the coast and on a more regular basis.

Sea-ice monitoring in Iceland

The sea ice that enters Icelandic waters is mainly winter ice from the Greenland Sea although older and thicker ice is frequently observed, as are icebergs. The presence of sea ice will enhance further ice formation in the region. There are great variations in the amount, extent and duration of the ice close to Iceland and the conditions can change very quickly. The reason for the variation is believed to be a combination of the amount of ice in the East Greenland Current, prevailing wind directions and the oceanic conditions near Iceland.

Regular sea-ice monitoring using satellite images has not been provided in Iceland. The Icelandic Coast Guard (ICG) maps the region during their ice-reconnaissance flights, several times per year (on average 18 charts per year during the last 5 years) and mainly when the ice is close to the coasts and when the need for information is greatest. The Icelandic Meteorological Office (IMO) receives ice observations from ships navigating in Icelandic waters and from coastal weather stations, when ice is in sight. It is the duty of captains to send reports to the IMO when ice is seen, but few of them do on a regular basis. The IMO issues sea-ice warnings when appropriate and broadcast ice information on the NAVTEX system, in the local radio and on their web page. The Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI)

publishes a sea-ice chart for the whole Greenland Sea weekly and these charts are used in Iceland. Furthermore, many captains have started to use different web sites to view satellite images and sea-ice information, mainly the pages provided by Leif Toudal at the Danish Technical University (DTU). This indicates that some captains need daily sea-ice charts for at least a part of the year.

Interviews with captains

The first priority of the project was to find out what kind of information was needed, when and how often. Twelve captains were interviewed, five of which were from small fishing boats (6-7 tons) fishing off the coast of the NW peninsula, four from trawlers (430-1318 tons), two of the captains were from the ICG's ships (1000 and 1200 tons) and one from a cargo ship circumnavigating Iceland and going to Europe and North America. All the interviews were taped and then written down afterwards.

The first question was on the ship: Size and ice strength.

The small fishing boats are not ice strengthened and will only navigate in newly formed grease ice. Only two of the trawlers, the shrimp trawlers that is, are ice strengthened and these will cross sea-ice bands and fields though they try to avoid it. The shrimp trawlers tend to fish near the ice edge, as oceanic conditions make living conditions for shrimp favourable there. The ships of the ICG are ice strengthened but the position of the propeller does not encourage encounters with ice. The ICG navigates in the whole region and will occasionally have to rescue ship from the ice. The cargo ship is not ice strengthened and will avoid sailing in ice-infested areas.

Question two: The need for sea-ice information: When, how often and where.

The captains of the small fishing boat do mainly need sea-ice information in the springtime when ice is usually closest to the coasts. Most of the captains of the trawlers mentioned the period from February to May though some mentioned a longer period, September to May. The ICG captains mentioned the whole year. Not so surprisingly, the region that most of the captains mentioned was the Denmark Strait and the sea off the NW peninsula and N Iceland. One of the captains stressed the fact that sea-ice information or warnings have to be available or issued before the ice reaches the fishing grounds and, not least, the main sailing route around Iceland.

Question three: Type of data needed.

All the captains mention the position of the main ice edge as the main type of information needed. The ice coverage came second and a few of the captains mention the type of ice and whether there are ice bands present. One captain mentioned the maximum extent of all ice, including icebergs. One of the captains on the shrimp trawlers said that he needed information with 10 nm accuracy in order to be able to decide if his fishing grounds were covered with ice or not. This could save him time and oil. He also said that he would like to have this information twice per day. Others mention the importance of knowing how fast the ice is moving. One captain said that inaccurate information was worse than no information.

Question four: Media

All the captains receive information on the ice via the NAVTEX system (text only) but one captain mentioned poor NAVTEX coverage North and East of Iceland. Many captains mentioned the radio and information received directly from coastal broadcasting stations. One captain mentioned the web page of the DMI, and two others mention the DTU web page. The captains of the small fishing boats mentioned the weather forecast on the television.

Question five: Experience of sea-ice information

All the captains stated that the ICG's ice charts were good and accurate, but not regular or frequent enough. A few of the captains mention that it would be valuable to receive ice charts more frequently, every three days would be a great improvement from the current status.

General comments

None of the captains had learned about the ice in school, it had only been mentioned briefly in the Maritime College in Reykjavík (Stýrimannaskólinn). The main learning process is through experience in sailing in ice and learning from other captains.

All the captains will exchange sea-ice information with other captains and perhaps with the ICG. They only send the IMO information if something unusual or hazardous is observed. Many other questions were asked, and they will be described in more detail in the final report.

The captains were also asked if they were willing to receive ice charts during the test period, and most of them did. The others were not planning to be in the region at that time.

Most of the interviews took place where it was possible to show the captains the different types of satellite images and explain to them their main qualities.

Satellite images

The next step was to decide the test period for mapping the sea-ice and ordering satellite images. Although radar imagery (SAR) is best for sea-ice monitoring, the price of the data is a problem. It was therefore decided to focus on images available at no cost on the internet, such as passive microwave images (SSM/I) and quickscat, as well as relatively inexpensive NOAA AVHRR images from the Tromsø Satellite Station (TSS), in order to make the service realistic and therefore possible to continue with it in Iceland. However, a limited number ERS-2 SAR images were ordered from the TSS for comparison with the other images. A two week period was selected, from April 10-24th.

Ice reconnaissance flights

The ICG were joined on their ice reconnaissance flights three times during the spring of 2002, in order to compare visual observations to satellite images and to learn more about the ice in the region during the period. A number of photographs were taken during the flights, and the height, speed and direction of the aircraft noted.

Sea-ice charts

During the test period, one or two ice charts were made every day. The schedule was to map the ice according to a Quickscat image from the day before, early in the morning, and then when NOAA AVHRR images were available in the early afternoon, improve the ice chart and then send it to the captains. The study included comparison of the two types of information, and the details thereof will be presented in the final report. Suffice to say, the images complimented each other well but there would be a slight problem with interpreting them when the region was covered with clouds (NOAA AVHRR images) and high wind speed (Quickscat). Unfortunately, it was not possible to use SSM/I or AMSU images from the DTU web page in this study since the data arrived so late (up to two days after the satellite pass). This has now been changed and in the future, both of these image types will be used as well.

The main information on the ice charts was the position of the ice edge, and rough estimate of the coverage. Ice bands were marked specially, and it was possible to see

where each “ice line” would stem from. There was a special warning stating that there might be ice bands, floes or icebergs closer to the coast than the map showed. The ice charts were only sent to captains that knew that this was an experiment, and they were asked not to pass them on to others unless explaining to them that the information might not be accurate.

Sending the ice charts

During most of the test period, two ships were fishing near the ice edge and they both received ice charts. For part of the time, one of the ships would receive the information and then pass it on to the other. The ice covered most of the fishing grounds in the first few days but later in the season it retreated and more ships arrived. At that time captains that had not been interviewed started calling asking for ice charts. They all received charts after being told about the possible limitations.

It was decided not to send the information out on NAVTEX, since the data was not official. The ice charts were sent via fax most of the time, but occasionally via e-mail (the position of the ice edge as a text messages) through a satellite phone. Unfortunately it was not possible to test Radiomidun’s service bank, due to programming difficulties. Radiomidun did however pass the e-mail messages on to the ships via their system. The ICG received the maps via normal e-mail, and they would also get ice charts with the satellite images as the background picture. The main problem with sending the information to the ships was in cases when the fax machine in the ship was not connected. It would then be necessary to call the ship and send the chart again. On few occasions the telephone connection would be too poor to send charts.

The captains send ice information back to the Science Institute where it was compared to the ice charts. The comparison was successful, the information agreed quite well. This is however, no guarantee that this would be the case all the time.

Second interviews

During the summer of 2002, four interviews were taken with captains that had received ice charts. They all agreed on the charts being useful, and potentially extremely useful in difficult situation. Many of them commented on the design of the charts, and these comments were then used to improve the design further.

Results

The overall result of the project was good, though it would have been interesting to use Radiomidun’s servicebank. The charts were not put on the internet since none of the captains that were interviewed planned to use it, but that would have been an easy task and has now begun. Since this is the first time that the sea-ice has been mapped on a daily basis near Iceland, the captains were possibly too positive towards the product and the service. The clearest sign of this project being quite successful is the fact that the demand for ice chart carried on throughout the summer, and in total 60 ice charts were published and sent to users, where only 14 had been planned.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank the Icelandic Coast Guard, all the captains involved in the project, the staff at the Tromso Satellite Station, the University of Iceland Research Fund for enabling the continuation of the project throughout the summer of 2002.

DRAFT 13 October 2002

Integrated Weather, Sea Ice and Ocean Service System (IWICOS)

IWICOS DEMONSTRATION REPORT:

Demonstration of near real time distribution of free weather, ice and ocean data over the Internet.

Leif Toudal & Roberto Saldo, Danish Center for Remote Sensing, Technical University of Denmark (DCRS/DTU)

Contract Number: IST-1999-11129

Ørsted•DTU
October 2002

Technical University of Denmark (DTU) Danish Center for Remote Sensing, Department of Electromagnetic Systems (EMI), Building 348, Technical University of Denmark, DK-2800 Lyngby, Denmark Phone: + 45 45881444 Fax: + 45 45931634 E-Mail: lt@emi.dtu.dk	
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INVESTIGATORS DTU/DCRS Leif Toudal and Roberto Saldo
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1. Background

Figure 1. Example of an SSM/I ice concentration image in the Interactive Java viewer.

Main objectives of the demonstration were:

- Use of standard software and hardware platforms
- Platform independency (JAVA software, standard web browser)
- Provide interactivity (user can tailor view of data)
- Demonstrate a near real time service running for an extended period of time
- Use freely available satellite data
- Supplement by freely available weather and wave forecast data
- Take into account the limited bandwidth of many users

The demonstration has taken place throughout the duration of the IWICOS project (2000-2002).

Figure 2. Example of a Quikscat polarization ratio image in the Interactive Java viewer.

2. Target user groups

The system was originally developed for internal use at DCRS. The purpose was to enable distance working, and to allow our data collection system to be supervised from remote places. Project partners and colleagues became very interested in the service, and we decided to open the system up for external use. We now see our main users as universities and other scientific institutions doing arctic research, operational ice centers, shipping companies, fisheries companies, etc. - people with a need for varied and timely information about the arctic marine environment.

Our target user group is expected to perform some interpretation of the images themselves, so we see our objectives as providing the tools to make decisions, rather than making the decisions.

3. Data Sources

All data are automatically gathered from the Internet. We are continuously looking for new data sources, to expand our coverage, to become independent of single sources, and to be able to include new facilities, higher resolution and/or more timely data.

The main sources are:

SSM/I data

The Global Hydrology Resource Center (GHRC) provides both historical and current Earth science data, information, and products from satellite, airborne, and surface-based instruments. The GHRC acquires basic data streams and produces derived products from many instruments spread across a variety of instrument platforms. The GHRC is supported by NASA and is the data management and user services arm of the Global Hydrology & Climate Center (GHCC) in Huntsville, Alabama.

QuikSCAT data

Quikscat scatterometer data are provided by IWICOS partner DMI. The data are provided as ascii files containing latitude and longitude coordinates, HH and VV backscatter as well as wind speed and direction.

AMSU data

The Cooperative Institute for Research in the Atmosphere, CIRA was established at Colorado State University in 1980 to increase the effectiveness of atmospheric research in areas of mutual interest between the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), Colorado State University and other groups.

CIRA operates an extensive satellite earthstation. CIRA's earthstation first collected GOES weather data in 1980. Since then, CIRA's earthstation has collected from each succeeding GOES satellite. Currently, CIRA collects GOES-8, and GOES-10. In addition to GOES, CIRA also collects conventional surface and upper air data, Meteosat, AMSU and AVHRR data. These data products are collected in their high resolution form for CIRA researchers.

NOAA AVHRR data

Tromsø Satellite Station AS. TSS operates two ground stations for downloading, processing, disseminating and storing of data from polar orbiting satellites. Based on data from satellites, TSS offers earth observation products and monitoring services to customers within our coverage area, in near real-time.

Sea Surface Temperature data

Top Karten. Zusammenstellung von für Europäer interessanten Wetterkarten (Analysen und Prognosen, Beobachtungen, Satbilder usw.). Die meisten selbst erzeugt. Original data from NOAA. <http://www.wetterzentrale.de>

Wind and Wave forecasts

The Marine Modeling and Analysis Branch is part of the Environmental Modeling Center, which is responsible for the development of improved numerical weather, marine, and climate prediction modeling systems within NCEP/NWS.

Provide analysis and real-time forecast guidance (1-16 days) on marine meteorological, oceanographic, and cryospheric parameters over the global oceans and coastal areas of the US.

Digital Ice Charts

The National Ice Center (NIC) is a multi-agency operational center representing the Department of Defense (Navy), the Department of Commerce's National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), and the Department of Transportation (Coast Guard). The NIC includes personnel from the National Environmental Satellite Data Information Service (NESDIS) within NOAA. The Navy component within NIC is called the Naval Ice Center (NAVICECEN) and is a fourth echelon command reporting directly to the Naval Oceanographic Office (NAVOCEANO) at the Stennis Space Center, Mississippi. Both NAVICECEN and NAVOCEANO are part of the Naval Meteorology and Oceanography Command, headquartered at the Stennis Space Center. The Commanding Officer of NAVICECEN also serves as the Director of the National Ice Center.

4. Production chain

Figure 3. The DTU/DCRS data production chain.

Data source	Daily throughput	
SSM/I	225 MB	
AMSU	80 MB	
QuikSCAT	20 MB	
Wave & wind forecasts	9 MB	
AVHRR quiklooks	15 MB	

Table 1. Typical daily data throughput.

The production chain produces images for our thin client solution (plain simple gif og jpg images to be viewed in Netscape or MSIE) as well as data for the balanced JAVA applet client and for the IWICOS broker system for other IWICOS partners. The number of individual data products per day exceeds 500 of which ca. 20 are for the thin client, and the remaining for various versions of the balanced client that allows the user to produce her own views.

5. User Interface

There are two main user interfaces, one for the thin client data (images), and one for the balanced client

Figure 4. Screenshot of main web page directing the user to the "interactive Ice browser" or the "latest" thin client images

The thin client images are primarily from the SSM/I instrument. Figure 5 shows an example of the thin client interface and a typical image product.

Figure 5. User interface and example of thin client product.

Another example of a thin client product is seen in figure 6.

The characteristics of the thin client products are that they are simple images with a land mask, a lat/lon grid, and a coastline and a minimum of annotation (date and time).

We have not for this demonstration spent time on refurbishing the thin client interface.

The main balanced client interface is seen in figure 7, and an example of the interactive screen is seen in figure 8. The total size of the JAVA applet is ca. 60 Kbytes, so it does not necessarily require a lot of data transfer to obtain considerable interactivity.

Figure 6. Example of AMSU mosaic as presented to the thin client.

Figure 7. The interface to the interactive system.

Figure 8. The balanced client user interface.

The balanced client allows the user to select date and pick data from the selected date. Subsequently a list of vector overlays such as coastlines, lat/lon grids, ice concentration contours, wind and wave forecasts, ice charts etc can be selected and toggled on/of. Colours of the selected overlays can be controlled individually to suit individual needs. The user can zoom in and out, and pan around in the image.

The screen view contains information areas such as colour legend, image info (date, time) and a vector legend. The user can click inside the satellite image, and lat/lon coordinates and parameter value (e.g. ice concentration) will be displayed in the image info panel.

6. User feedback / Web statistics

Most user feedback has been in connection with the (few) down periods we have had over the past year. A number of items in the view has been introduced as a response to user feedback. Examples are:

- Colour legend
- Date selection
- Image info

Users also have complained about the many subareas, and the long list of images. We are therefore in the process of switching to just two databases/interfaces, one for the northern, and one for the southern hemisphere (see figures 1+2).

We appreciate user feedback, and we use user suggestions to improve the service.

Figure 9. User statistics for July 2002. (Number of image data files transferred pr. day).

Figure 9 and 10 shows a typical example of usage statistics for the month of July 2002. The usage typically drops during week-ends.

Note a substantial use from Argentina during this period where the Argentinian Naval Icebreaker *Almirante Irizar* were contracted to try to rescue the German supply vessel *MS Magdalena Oldendorff* stuck in the ice near Antarctica.

Top 154 of 261 Total Sites									
#	Hits	Files	KBytes	Visits	Hostname				
1	364	14.39%	336	14.91%	33211	26.33%	0	0.00%	Woods_Hole_Oceanographic_Institution.edu
2	176	6.96%	171	7.59%	5957	4.72%	0	0.00%	telia.com
3	156	6.17%	137	6.08%	4417	3.50%	0	0.00%	ras.tele.dk
4	133	5.26%	115	5.10%	5309	4.21%	0	0.00%	TELE_Greenland_Internet.gl
5	125	4.94%	93	4.13%	5279	4.19%	0	0.00%	dip.t-dialin.net
6	111	4.39%	99	4.39%	7731	6.13%	0	0.00%	Armada_Argentina.ar
7	102	4.03%	91	4.04%	5217	4.14%	0	0.00%	Unisoft_Murmansk.ru
8	91	3.60%	9	0.40%	632	0.50%	0	0.00%	pe244175.user.veloxzone.com.br
9	79	3.12%	75	3.33%	1969	1.56%	0	0.00%	qvest.net
10	77	3.04%	77	3.42%	5141	4.08%	0	0.00%	Telecom_Soluciones.ar
11	63	2.49%	62	2.75%	3360	2.66%	0	0.00%	Wanadoo_Internet.fr
12	58	2.29%	54	2.40%	1652	1.31%	0	0.00%	Icelandic_Meteorological_Institute.is
13	57	2.25%	55	2.44%	1959	1.55%	0	0.00%	Energetyka-Kaliska.pl
14	57	2.25%	57	2.53%	2817	2.23%	0	0.00%	University_of_Iceland.is
15	46	1.82%	30	1.33%	1451	1.15%	0	0.00%	Warsaw_University_of_Technology.pl
16	35	1.38%	35	1.55%	2309	1.83%	0	0.00%	Skyrr.is
17	34	1.34%	34	1.51%	1868	1.48%	0	0.00%	Norwegian_Polar_Institute.no
18	29	1.15%	29	1.29%	1156	0.92%	0	0.00%	mstu.edu.ru
19	25	0.99%	24	1.07%	2411	1.91%	0	0.00%	Arctic_Antarctic_Research_Institute.ru
20	23	0.91%	16	0.71%	573	0.45%	0	0.00%	Mimer_Internet.no
21	22	0.87%	15	0.67%	1458	1.16%	0	0.00%	British_Antarctic_Survey.uk
22	22	0.87%	22	0.98%	1518	1.20%	0	0.00%	host182018.arnet.net.ar
23	22	0.87%	22	0.98%	1035	0.82%	0	0.00%	wppgmb01dc2-res-21-186.mts.net
24	21	0.83%	21	0.93%	1083	0.86%	0	0.00%	cacheflow.kpn.com
25	21	0.83%	21	0.93%	1171	0.93%	0	0.00%	fmr155.fmr.is
26	20	0.79%	20	0.89%	1070	0.85%	0	0.00%	Icelandic_University_Research_Network.is
27	17	0.67%	17	0.75%	814	0.65%	0	0.00%	Iceland_Telecom.is
28	16	0.63%	16	0.71%	1058	0.84%	0	0.00%	Universitaet_Bremen.de
29	15	0.59%	15	0.67%	964	0.76%	0	0.00%	inar.ru
30	14	0.55%	14	0.62%	1248	0.99%	0	0.00%	200.43.229.1
31	14	0.55%	14	0.62%	527	0.42%	0	0.00%	213.78.100.11
32	14	0.55%	9	0.40%	205	0.16%	0	0.00%	Alfred_Wegener_Institut_(AWI).de
33	14	0.55%	14	0.62%	357	0.28%	0	0.00%	cpe00045af32f77.cpe.net.cable.rogers.com
34	14	0.55%	14	0.62%	777	0.62%	0	0.00%	ppp195-241-31-109.dial.12move.nl
35	12	0.47%	11	0.49%	366	0.29%	0	0.00%	Scott_Polar_Research_Institute.uk
36	12	0.47%	11	0.49%	437	0.35%	0	0.00%	p17.hh.shuttle.de
37	11	0.43%	11	0.49%	435	0.35%	0	0.00%	GRICS_Canadian_School_Project.ca
38	11	0.43%	11	0.49%	369	0.29%	0	0.00%	ppp148.piuha.net
39	11	0.43%	10	0.44%	419	0.33%	0	0.00%	tin.it
40	10	0.40%	10	0.44%	458	0.36%	0	0.00%	193.41.132.130

Figure 10. User statistics for July 2002. (Number of image data files transferred).

Examples of main users within the target user groups:

- 1. Scientists involved in polar research**
 - a. University of Iceland (IS)
 - b. University of the Witwatersrand (ZA)
 - c. Harvard University (US)
 - d. Universite Catholique de Louvain (B)
 - e. Svalbard University (N)
 - f. Maritime University of Gdynia (PL)
 - g. Universität Hamburg (D)
 - h. Southampton University (UK)

- 2. Operational ice centers**
 - a. Danish Meteorological Institute
 - b. Finnish Institute for Marine Research
 - c. Icelandic Meteorological Office
 - d. US National Ice Center
 - e. Norwegian Meteorological Institute
 - f. UK Met office
 - g. Canadian Ice Service
 - h. German Ice Service (BSH)

- 3. Polar research institutions**
 - a. British Antarctic Survey (UK)
 - b. Arctic and Antarctic Research Institute (RU)
 - c. Woods_Hole_Oceanographic_Institution (US)
 - d. Scott Polar Research Institute (UK)
 - e. Institut français de recherche pour l'exploitation de la mer (IFREMER)
 - f. Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI)
 - g. Baltic Sea Research Institute (Warnemünde)
 - h. Deutsche Klimarechenzentrum
 - i. Norwegian Polar Institute
 - j. Department of Fisheries and Oceans (CDN)

- 4. Shipping companies**
 - a. Armada_Argentina
 - b. Murmansk_Shipping_Copmany
 - c. Princess Cruises

- 5. Fisheries**
 - a. Numerous internet providers from Norway, Iceland, Greenland, Russia.
 - b. Ocean Prawns A/S

- 6. Insurance companies**
 - a. Bergens Skibsassuransforening (N)
 - b. Unifas Gjensidige Assuransforening (N)

- 7. Oil companies etc.**
 - a. Exxon
 - b. British Petroleum
 - c. Kolenergo Murmansk
 - d. Boliden Minerals (S)
 - e. Greenlands Power Supply
 - f. Statoll

7. Conclusions

It has been demonstrated that a free internet service with ice/sea/weather information can be established and it has attracted a large number of users in many fields.

The system has proven valuable for internal use as well as for many external users.

Running the system, we have gained considerable goodwill amongst science partners and collaborators all over the world.